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Green technology and productivity in European regions: the role of technological and scientific capabilities

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Abstract

Reconciling economic productivity with environmental sustainability represents a key challenge for regional development, particularly in the context of green transitions. This paper examines how green technologies and regional capabilities shape both labour productivity and environmental productivity across 221 European NUTS-2 regions from 1990 to 2019. Using panel data and fixed-effects models with lag structures, we investigate the direct and mediating effects of three types of capabilities: general technological, green-specific technological, and environmental scientific. The findings offer partial support for the dynamic version of the Porter Hypothesis showing that green technologies significantly enhance environmental productivity in the long term, while their impact on labour productivity is positive but short-lived. General technological capabilities have strong, cumulative effects on both environmental and labour productivity. Green-specific capabilities yield more modest and lagged impacts, whereas environmental scientific capabilities, captured through publication activity, exert highly delayed but significant positive effects on environmental productivity, and weaker, medium-term effects on labour productivity. Moreover, regional capabilities positively mediate the effect of green technologies on environmental productivity. These results highlight the importance of place-based innovation strategies that not only promote the development and adoption of green technologies, but also strengthen the underlying technological and scientific capabilities needed to support long-term sustainable productivity growth.

1. Introduction

In light of escalating climate change challenges, addressing both adaptation and greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions reduction—alongside other environmental threats—is crucial. Environmental innovations (EIs), particularly green technologies (GTs), are pivotal to these efforts due to their potential to improve environmental performance (Ekins, 2010; OECD, 2009).¹

Recent official reports from European and national institutes confirm marked regional disparities in both economic and environmental terms (EC, 2024; EEA, 2018; European Committee of the Regions, 2024). Evidence suggests that European regions do not have the same capacity to reconcile growing economic performance with a reduction in environmental impact. In this context, policy interventions are essential to address the *double externality* problem, which highlights firms' limited ability to internalize the environmental benefits from GT diffusion (Rennings, 2000).² This rationale supports the strong version of the Porter Hypothesis (PH), which posits that environmental regulation (ER) not only stimulates innovation—as in the weak version of the PH (Lanoie et al., 2011; Morales-Lage et al., 2016; Van Leeuwen and Mohnen, 2017)—but also offsets compliance costs and improves firm performance, typically measured by productivity (Porter and Linde, 1995; Van Leeuwen and Mohnen, 2017; Wang et al., 2019).

Much of the literature emphasises the role of policy intervention as a key driver of EIs (e.g., Acemoglu et al., 2012; Popp, 2002,0), often under the implicit assumption that it naturally leads to simultaneous gains in economic and environmental productivity.³ However, empirical support for the strong PH remains limited and mixed. While ER can foster innovation—particularly under flexible regimes—its ability to deliver “win-win” outcomes that also boost productivity is far from assured. GTs often yield short-term gains in environmental productivity, but their long-term effects—particularly on economic productivity—are less clear and evidence remains fragmented (e.g., Ghisetti and Quatraro, 2017; Marin, 2014; Marin and Lotti, 2016; Soltmann et al., 2015). In

¹ A widely cited definition of EI is “the production, assimilation or exploitation of a product, production process, service or management or business methods that is novel to the firm [or organisation] and which results, throughout its life cycle, in a reduction of environmental risk, pollution and other negative impacts of resources use (including energy use) compared to relevant alternatives” (Kemp and Pearson, 2007).

² The double externality problem refers to the fact that EIs generate (1) knowledge spillovers in the innovation phase—a classic market failure where firms cannot fully appropriate the benefits of their inventions—and (2) non-internalized environmental benefits in the diffusion phase, which are positive externalities for society but not rewarded by the market (Rennings, 2000).

³ While productivity typically refers to the ratio of outputs (goods and services) to inputs (such as labour, capital, and materials) (OECD, 2008), we define economic productivity in terms of economic performance (e.g., labour productivity, or total factor productivity) (e.g., Diewert and Nakamura, 2007), and environmental productivity as the efficiency of output relative to environmental impact (e.g., carbon productivity, or total-factor carbon productivity) (e.g., Du and Li, 2019; Ghisetti and Quatraro, 2017; Ghisetti and Rennings, 2014; Repetto, 1990).

this direction, the SPES project offers a sustainability-oriented perspective, promoting policy interventions aimed at reconciling economic productivity with environmental protection (Biggeri et al., 2023), aligning with key dimensions of the ongoing debate on IEs.

Against this backdrop, the present paper pursues a twofold objective. First, we examine the effects of GTs on both labour productivity (as a proxy for economic productivity) and environmental productivity across European regions. Second, we explore the direct and mediating role of regional capabilities—technological, green-specific technological, and environmental scientific—in shaping these effects. This aligns with ongoing efforts under the European Green Deal’s carbon neutrality goals by 2050 (Palaria, 2022), and the Joint Research Centre’s call for regionally tailored innovation and sustainability strategies (JRC, 2021).

To this end, we conduct a panel analysis of 221 NUTS-2 European regions across 25 European countries (2000 - 2019), using fixed-effects model. To examine long-run dynamics of green technologies (GTs), regional technological and scientific capabilities on productivity outcomes, we estimate finite distributed lag regressions.⁴ GTs are proxied by green patents filed at the European Patent Office (EPO), extracted from the REGPAT database (Haščič and Migotto, 2015; Maraut et al., 2008), and environmental scientific capabilities are proxied by environment-related scientific publications, extracted from the OpenAlex database (Priem et al., 2022).

In parallel, the paper zooms in on the roles played by regional technological and scientific capabilities in shaping the relationship between GTs and both productivity measures. This remains an underexplored area, yet it is essential for understanding why regions respond differently to similar policies. Regional capabilities—such as skills, knowledge, and institutions—have been recognized to influence innovation outcomes (e.g., Barbieri et al., 2020; Jaffe, 2014). In this context, the ability to recombine regional capabilities is central to the development of complex technologies (Balland and Rigby, 2017), such as GTs, which are generally more complex than their conventional counterparts (Barbieri et al., 2020). Economic Complexity (EC) methods have proven effective in quantifying technological capabilities across various spatial scales, including recent applications to environmental technologies and products (e.g. Barbieri et al., 2023; de Cunzio et al., 2022; Mealy and Teytelboym, 2022; Sbardella et al., 2018).

Next, we also consider the role of regional scientific capabilities—particularly in environmental fields—which remain largely absent from current empirical studies.⁵ Given the well-documented link between science and innovation (Marx and Fuegi, 2022), especially in the context of GTs, it is important to raise the question of whether regional environment-related scientific capabilities

⁴ We extend the analysis back to 1990 for the lag structure of explanatory variables.

⁵ Environmental science can be defined as "an interdisciplinary field of study which attempts to measure and evaluate the impact of man on the structure and function of social and ecological systems, and which focuses upon the management of these systems for their benefit and survival" (Barrett and Puchy, 1977).

also enhance productivity and mediate the gains associated with GTs.

Our findings can be summarized as follows. GTs are positively associated with environmental productivity, with effects cumulating over time. In contrast, their effect on labour productivity is weaker: we find positive short-term gains and limited evidence of longer-term effects. General technological capabilities are positively associated with both productivity outcomes. They show immediate effects on labour productivity and delayed effects on environmental productivity, both cumulating over time – with a stronger impact for labour productivity. Conversely, green-specific technological capabilities appear to support both productivity outcomes, but less consistently, with no robust evidence of broader long-term gains. Environment-related scientific capabilities are positively associated with environmental productivity, exerting both direct and highly delayed ($t - 15$) effects. The cumulative effects evidenced for labour productivity suggests a positive but weaker medium-term effect. All three capabilities positively mediate GTs in enhancing EP. Results are robust to alternative capability measures and model specifications.

The remainder of the paper is structured as follows. [Section 2](#) reviews the relevant literature on the productivity effects of GTs and the role of regional capabilities. [Section 3](#) describes the data. [Section 4](#) outlines the empirical methodology and construction of key variables. [Section 5](#) presents the main results, including robustness checks. [Section 6](#) concludes and discusses.

2. Literature review

Section 2. reviews the theoretical and empirical literature on the productivity effects of GTs and the role of local capabilities. Given the paper’s dual focus on labour and environmental productivity, the review is organized into four subsections. Section 2.1. discusses the economic implications of GTs, followed by their impact on environmental productivity in Section 2.2.. Section 2.3. examines the role of local technological capabilities, distinguishing between general and green-specific dimensions. Finally, Section 2.4. explores the emerging literature on local scientific capabilities, with a particular focus on environmental science. Each subsection concludes with a set of hypotheses tested in the empirical analysis, based on the context of European regions. In line with this structure, we hypothesize that (1) GTs positively influence both productivity outcomes, though with differing temporal dynamics and potentially varying effect signs; (2) regional technological and scientific capabilities directly enhance productivity; and (3) these capabilities positively mediate the effect of GTs on productivity outcomes.

Figure 2.1. Conceptual framework: the effect of green technology on productivity and the role of regional capabilities

2.1. Green technology and economic productivity

A large body of literature emphasizes the role of policy intervention as a driver of eco-innovation (EI, e.g., Acemoglu et al., 2012; Popp, 2002,0), often under the implicit assumption that fostering the development and adoption of EIs naturally leads to joint improvements in economic and environmental performance (e.g., Barbieri et al., 2016; Porter and Linde, 1995). Empirical evidence on the relationship between green technology (GT)—a subset of EI often proxied by patent data (e.g., Barbieri et al., 2016; Kemp and Pontoglio, 2011)—and economic productivity remains mixed. In

the short run, several studies find either no significant effect or lower productivity gains relative to conventional technologies, particularly in pollution-intensive industries facing stricter environmental regulation (Marin, 2014; Marin and Lotti, 2016). A key explanation for the non-significant or even reduced short-term productivity gains is the crowding-out effect: environmental regulations impose additional costs on firms (e.g., production adjustments, emissions compliance), which may divert resources from more profitable or productivity-enhancing innovations. As a result, compliance-oriented innovations may crowd out more value-generating innovation activities.

However, the type of GT adopted is crucial to its effect on economic productivity. While compliance-driven innovations typically yield limited economic productivity gains, energy and resource efficiency innovations tend to enhance productivity by reducing input costs and improving process efficiency—particularly through lower energy and material consumption (Ghisetti and Rennings, 2014; Rexhäuser and Rammer, 2014; Van Leeuwen and Mohnen, 2017). Empirical evidence on the dynamic nature of the PH—which posits that the positive effects of regulation-induced EI on productivity materialise only over time—remains limited (Lanoie et al., 2008). Soltmann et al. (2015) find that the accumulation of green knowledge—measured by the cumulative count of green patents—may result in a U-shaped relationship with economic productivity, proxied by industry-level value added. Initial investments in GTs may reduce productivity, but long-term gains emerge as firms adapt and optimize processes through learning and scale effects. However, the turning point is relatively high, implying that such benefits are only realized once firms or industries accumulate a critical mass of green knowledge. Piekkola and Rahko (2024) also provide recent support for the dynamic PH, showing that the productivity effects of EIs in Finish firms across a broad range of industries emerge with a time lag, becoming particularly stronger when measured with a two-period delay.

Overall, while the short-term productivity effects of GTs remain ambiguous and dependent on the type of technology, long-term outcomes appear more favorable—particularly once a critical threshold of accumulated green knowledge is reached. The dynamic nature of the PH may also apply in the context of European regions. Based on these considerations, we posit that a higher presence of GT-associated innovations within European regions may lead to either lower or higher levels of economic productivity. We therefore propose the following initial hypotheses:

H1.a: Green technologies are positively associated with economic productivity.

H1.b: Green technologies are negatively associated with economic productivity.

2.2. Green technology and environmental productivity

Against the backdrop of escalating climate challenges, the relationship between GTs and productivity is increasingly investigated in relation to environmental sustainability. Although the concept of environmental productivity (EP) lacks a consensual definition, it is generally understood as the efficiency with which economic output is generated relative to environmental impact (Du and Li, 2019; Ghisetti and Rennings, 2014; Repetto, 1990).

Among empirical proxies for EP, one of the most widely used is carbon productivity, which captures the ability to increase economic output while reducing carbon emissions (e.g., Du and Li, 2019). While direct evidence linking GTs and EP remains limited, existing studies consistently report a positive relationship (Ghisetti and Quatraro, 2017; Liu et al., 2022).

At a global scale, Du and Li (2019) examine the impact of GTs—measured by green patent stocks per capita—on total-factor carbon productivity (TFCP) across 71 countries. Their results indicate that GTs have a significant and positive effect on TFCP, but only in high-income economies. Two primary mechanisms are proposed. First, in low- and middle-income countries, economic priorities (e.g., growth, poverty alleviation, fossil fuel subsidies) and high adoption costs act as barriers to effective GT uptake. In contrast, high-income economies benefit from stronger environmental awareness and market-based energy pricing, which generate greater incentives for adoption. Second, the adoption of GTs requires innovations ecosystems, which are more prevalent in high-income economies, where related advanced complementary innovations and inter-sectoral linkages—through technological spillovers (Neves and Sequeira, 2018) or systemic complementarities (Geels et al., 2004)—facilitate GTs adoption. In addition, similar to its effect on economic productivity, the dynamic PH may also apply to environment outcomes, with greater improvements emerging over time as firms adapt GTs into their processes (Ambec et al., 2013; Lanoie et al., 2008).

Overall, existing evidence suggests that GTs enhance EP, particularly in high-income economies where complementary innovations and supportive policies facilitate adoption. The dynamic PH may similarly apply to EP in the context of European regions. Based on these considerations, we posit that a higher presence of GT-associated innovations within European regions may lead to higher levels of EP. We therefore propose the following hypothesis:

H1.bis: Green technologies are positively associated with environmental productivity.

2.3. The role of local technological capabilities in productivity

The development of GTs involves recombining distant and cognitively diverse knowledge domains (Fusillo, 2019), contributing to their generally greater complexity compared to conventional technologies (Barbieri et al., 2020). Fusillo (2019) identifies three key sources of this complexity: a lack of established standards and accepted solutions; the need to address multiple technical-economic challenges alongside stringent regulatory requirements; and the hybridization of green and dirty technologies in new and creative ways. These features expand the cognitive distance between knowledge domains and increase the number and diversity of components involved in innovation.

The generally higher complexity of GTs highlights the potential role of local technological capabilities, particularly, their potential mediating effect on the relationship between GTs and productivity dynamics. The Economic Complexity (EC) framework offers a useful lens through which to understand the importance of such capabilities. In this framework, capabilities typically refer to the often intangible, place-specific forms of productive knowledge—such as resources, skills, infrastructure, and know-how—that enable the generation of complex products or technologies. These capabilities are difficult to observe directly and tend to evolve path-dependently (Hausmann et al., 2014; Hidalgo and Hausmann, 2009; Tacchella et al., 2012). The EC framework posits that a product is a reflection of the set of capabilities required to produce it, and that more complex economies are those that produce a greater diversity of products that are less ubiquitous (Hidalgo and Hausmann, 2009). More recent applications emphasize not only the presence of capabilities but also the ability to recombine them, which is central to the generation of complex technologies (Balland and Rigby, 2017). While initially applied to export data to capture productive capabilities (Hidalgo and Hausmann, 2009), the EC framework has since been extended to patent data to assess technological capabilities, which reflect the global structure of specialization in patent classes (Balland and Rigby, 2017). To our knowledge, whether technological capabilities influence productivity remains underexplored. However, both economic and environmental dimensions of productivity have been positively linked to EC in existing research.

Regarding economic performance, EC is strongly correlated with GDP per capita and has predictive power for future GDP growth (Cristelli et al., 2013; Hidalgo and Hausmann, 2009; Tacchella et al., 2012,1). For environmental performance, more complex economies may be better equipped to mitigate GHG emissions, as EC positively correlates with the generation of more efficient and less polluting products (e.g., Mealy and Teytelboym, 2022; Romero and Gramkow, 2021), although empirical evidence remains mixed. An inverted U-shaped relationship between EC and CO₂ emissions—consistent with the Environmental Kuznets Curve (EKC) hypothesis—has been observed (Boleti et al., 2021; Neagu, 2019). Doğan et al. (2019) suggest that EC tends to increase environmental degradation in low- and middle-income countries but contributes to CO₂ reduction in high-income economies. This pattern is corroborated by Aluko et al. (2023), who

identify an income threshold beyond which EC supports environmental improvements.

However, although EC is a necessary condition for the development and adoption of GTs, it does not guarantee a green economic orientation. While most studies focus on whether complex economies are better positioned to respond to environmental challenges, [Mealy and Teytelboym \(2022\)](#) shift the emphasis toward identifying which countries possess the capabilities needed to thrive in the green economy and how they might reorient their industrial structures for green competitiveness. To this end, they introduce the Green Complexity Index (GCI) as an alternative metric within the EC framework and apply it to export product data. Whereas the ECI captures overall capabilities, the GCI identifies economies that have accumulated green-specific capabilities. Considering both metrics is essential, as they measure related but distinct phenomena. [Mealy and Teytelboym \(2022\)](#)'s analysis show that while ECI is strongly correlated with GDP per capita, it does not directly reflect environmental outcomes. In contrast, the GCI correlates positively with green patenting and lower CO₂ emissions, reinforcing its value as an indicator of green competitiveness. Their findings also show that high ECI does not guarantee high GCI. For example, petroleum and oil-exporting countries such as Qatar, Australia and Kuwait exhibit high ECI scores despite low GCI scores. This indicates that while these countries are leaders in terms of technological complexity, they are not oriented toward environmental sustainability. In contrast, Germany and South Korea score highly on both dimensions, underscoring their ability to be leaders in sophisticated and competitive sectors, including those environmentally oriented. Based on GCI, the study also highlights the strong path-dependent nature of green diversification—early success in developing green production capabilities tends to foster further green production.

Therefore, the generally higher complexity of GTs underscores the possible importance of local technological capabilities—and especially green technological capabilities—as captured by the EC framework, in supporting their development and adoption. Although the relationship between technological capabilities and productivity remains underexplored, existing literature shows positive associations between EC and both economic and environmental dimensions of productivity. Moreover, while EC is a necessary condition for the development and adoption of GTs, it does not automatically translate into a green economic orientation, which is better captured by the GCI. Based on these arguments, we posit that higher complexity—and particularly green complexity—within European regions may lead to higher levels of economic and environmental productivity. Furthermore, we hypothesize that they may positively mediate the relationship between GT adoption and economic and environmental productivity. We therefore propose the following four hypotheses:

H2: Regional technological capabilities are positively associated with productivity.

H2.bis: Regional technological capabilities combined with green technologies are positively associated with productivity.

H3: Regional green technological capabilities are positively associated with productivity.

H3.bis: Regional green technological capabilities combined with green technologies are positively associated with productivity.

2.4. The role of local scientific capabilities in productivity

The role of local scientific capabilities—such as those measured by the stock of scientific knowledge—is not explicitly captured within the EC framework, which primarily infers productive or technological capabilities from observed exports or patents.⁶ Scientific capabilities may reflect both human capital (e.g., skills, expertise) and institutional capacity (e.g., universities, research laboratories), and are inherently path- and place-dependent, as shown for European NUTS-2 regions (Heimeriks et al., 2019). The contribution of science—and environmental science in particular—to productivity remains, to our knowledge, underexplored.⁷ However, given the well-established relationship between scientific research and innovation, further investigation into its direct and potential mediating role in enhancing productivity is warranted.

Scientific knowledge underpins technological progress (e.g., Jaffe, 2014), and plays a central role in the development of new technological knowledge (Sorenson and Fleming, 2004). Ahmadpoor and Jones (2017) show that scientific knowledge, although often transmitted indirectly—spanning two to four degrees of citation—underlies high-impact technologies. Scientific knowledge has become increasingly embedded in technological development (Wang and Li, 2021), and while the degree of dependence varies across domains (Heimeriks and Balland, 2016), it appears especially salient in emerging ones such as renewable energy technologies (Fernández et al., 2022; Moreno and Ocampo-Corrales, 2022).

Additionally, academic inventors act as interfaces between science and GTs development (Quatraro, 2019). They contribute through their education, broad knowledge base, and cross-domain expertise, which facilitate access and processing of GT-related knowledge. Additionally, they

⁶ In this paper, we use the terms *scientific knowledge* and *scientific capability* interchangeably, as the former serves as a proxy for the latter.

⁷ Environmental science can be defined as "an interdisciplinary field of study which attempts to measure and evaluate the impact of man on the structure and function of social and ecological systems, and which focuses upon the management of these systems for their benefit and survival" (Barrett and Puchy, 1977).

may compensate for weak recombinant technological capabilities: in Italian NUTS-3 regions, Orsatti et al. (2023) find that academic inventors positively influence green regional diversification (i.e., the entry of regions into new GT specializations), with the strongest effects in regions lacking such capabilities. To date, however, the relationship between environmental scientific capabilities, GTs, and productivity remains unexamined. Particularly, local scientific knowledge may play a critical role. Bergeaud and Guillouzouic (2024) find in the French regional context that firms geographically close to scientific production—particularly in related fields—are more likely to innovate, especially in science-based sectors such as biotechnology. Henceforth, geographical proximity between science and industry fosters knowledge spillovers, even without direct collaboration. It is therefore plausible that local environmental scientific capabilities may similarly mediate green technological development and indirectly influence productivity.

This perspective raises the question of whether local environmental scientific capabilities, as measured by scientific knowledge production, can also enhance productivity and mediate the impact of GTs on productivity in European regions. Although such effects may be indirect and subject to time lags, environmental scientific capabilities may provide a critical foundation for GT development, support environmental practices, and ultimately improve both economic and environmental productivity. Based on these arguments, we posit that higher levels of environmental scientific capabilities—as proxied by scientific knowledge production—may lead to higher economic and environmental productivity. Furthermore, we hypothesize that environmental scientific capabilities may positively mediate the relationship between GT and both economic and environmental productivity. We therefore propose the following two hypotheses:

H4: Regional environmental scientific capabilities are positively associated with productivity.

H4.bis: Regional environmental scientific capabilities combined with green technologies are positively associated with productivity.

3. Data

Our primary data source is the OECD REGPAT database (January 2024 release). While patent data has well-known limitations in capturing innovation—such as the inability to capture non-patentable innovations, variation in patent quality across technologies, the influence of firm-level behaviours, and the presence of industry-specific biases—it remains one of the most robust and widely used proxies for environmental innovation (Haščič and Migotto, 2015). We extract relevant patents in four key steps: (1) We identify "green" patents as those that include at least one Cooperative Patent Classification (CPC) application code belonging to the "Y02" or "Y04S" classes in the first four digits (Veefkind et al., 2012).⁸ The CPC system provides a hierarchical classification scheme, enabling detailed identification of patent content at increasing levels of granularity. (2) We restrict the sample to patents filed at the European Patent Office (EPO) to ensure result homogeneity and comparability in patent quality. (3) We include only patents with a priority date between 2000 and 2019 (inclusive), representing the first filing date closest to the European inventor's idea.⁹ (4) We focus on patents with a European origin, defined as those with inventors located in the EU-27, the UK, Norway and Switzerland.¹⁰ We assign each patents to a NUTS-2 region based on the inventor's address rather than that of the applicant. This approach accounts for the increasing number of patents in which applicants and inventors are based in different countries. This trend is primarily driven by the internationalization of R&D activities within multinational corporations (De Rassenfosse and Seliger, 2020). To address patents with inventors coming from different countries, we apply a fractional counting approach. For example, if a patent has two inventors in two different countries, it assigns a weight of 0.5 to each location. To improve cross-regional comparability, we excluded 22 small European island regions, considered as statistical outliers.¹¹ Finally, all NUTS-2 regions are updated according to the NUTS 2021 classification to ensure temporal consistency over time. In cases where regional boundaries or codes have changed across versions, we proportionally redistribute the fractional patent counts based on updated mappings.¹²

⁸ This selection covers nine GTs classes: Adaptation to climate change (Y02A), Energy-efficient buildings (Y02B), Carbon capture and storage (Y02C), Energy-efficient ICT (Y02D), Renewable and nuclear energy generation (Y02E), Emission reduction in industry (Y02P), Low-carbon transport (Y02T), Waste management (Y02W), and Smart grids (Y04S).

⁹ The patent extraction has been extended back to 1990 for the temporal dynamics analysis.

¹⁰ For the global rankings of ECI and GCI, we also extracted patents linked to global NUTS-2 regions.

¹¹ The 22 excluded regions include: the Azores (PT20), Madeira (PT30), Guadeloupe (FRY1), Martinique (FRY2), French Guiana (FRY3), La Réunion (FRY4), Mayotte (FRY5), Saint-Martin (FRM0), North Aegean (EL41) and South Aegean (EL42), Crete (EL43), Ionian Islands (EL62), Balearic Islands (ES53), Ceuta (ES63), Melilla (ES64), Canary Islands (ES70), Åland (FI20), Sicily (ITG1), Sardinia (ITG2), Malta (MT00), and Cyprus (CY00).

¹² Regional reclassification is performed using the nuts package in R: <https://cran.r-project.org/web/packages/nuts/nuts.pdf>.

Scientific publications serve as a proxy for the scientific knowledge production and the underlying scientific capabilities of a region. Publication counts are extracted from OpenAlex, a robust open-source platform with comprehensive coverage of scholarly research (Priem et al., 2022). Specifically, we count articles published in English-writing between 2000 and 2019, based on the institutional affiliations of European authors (EU-27, the UK, Norway, and Switzerland) identified through the Research Organization Registry (ROR) identifier.¹³ We exclude publications affiliated with the Centre National de la Recherche Scientifique (CNRS), France's largest public research organization, as an outlier. CNRS is not a single-location institution but a decentralized network of research units embedded in universities and institutions across multiple NUTS-2 regions. As a result, its high publication volume is often geocoded to its headquarters in Île-de-France, artificially inflating that region's research output.¹⁴

Environmental-related scientific publications are defined as those tagged "Environmental science" by the Microsoft Academic Graph (MAG).¹⁵ Given the automatic tagging of higher order hierarchies, such concepts are more likely to be assigned. Therefore, OpenAlex provides a correspondence score for each concept at the publication level; we adopt the recommended 0.3 threshold for analysis (i.e., publications must exhibit at least 30% correspondence with the "Environmental science" concept, e.g., Korte et al., 2023).

We applied a spatial join to link institutions to European NUTS-2 regions, using a full-counting approach, based on their geographic coordinates. Specifically, we extracted the latitude and longitude of each institution publishing environmental scientific articles from OpenAlex and converted these coordinates into spatial point objects. Using the Eurostat NUTS 2021 GIS shapefile, we then identified the corresponding NUTS-2 region as the polygon containing each spatial point.

¹³ As with patents, the extraction of scientific publications has been extended back to 1990 for the temporal dynamics analysis.

¹⁴ While we acknowledge that similar issues may apply to other institutions, only CNRS was excluded due its disproportionately high publication volume to the rest of the distribution, which would significantly distort the overall picture.

¹⁵ MAG, incorporated into OpenAlex and based on the HEER deep-learning model, provides a hierarchical, tree-structured classification of concepts, automatically assigning publications to one or more categories across five levels of aggregation in a robust way: "The number of papers indexed by MAS, for instance, has grown from low tens of millions to 83 million while maintaining an above 95% accuracy based on test data sets derived from academic activities at Microsoft Research." (Sinha et al., 2015). Environmental science is one of the nineteen top-level concepts in the classification hierarchy (OpenAlex, 2022). Environmental science is defined as *interdisciplinary field that studies human interaction with the environment* (<https://openalex.org/concepts/C39432304>). As a robustness check, we also implemented an alternative approach based on keywords. We selected publications containing a list of environmental-related terms in the title, abstract, or keywords, irrespective of case. The list includes: "climate change", "climate risk", "global warming", "climate mitigation", "climate adaptation", "climate resilience", "carbon neutrality", "net zero emissions", "de-carbonization", "renewable energy", "energy efficiency", "green technology", "clean technology", "carbon emissions", "greenhouse gases", and "carbon capture and storage".

The coordinates of both the institutions and the NUTS2 regions were projected into the same European coordinate reference system (EPSG:3035). In cases where institutions were located near coastlines and could not be matched directly to a polygon, we assigned the geographically nearest NUTS-2 region.¹⁶

As an alternative measure, we examine whether the scientific capabilities underpinning GTs are environment-related and how they are distributed across European regions, indicating varying degrees of alignment between GTs and environment-related science. To connect GTs and scientific capabilities, we use patent-to-paper citations from the Reliance on Science project.¹⁷ Specifically, we conducted two extractions. First, we extracted citations from EPO patents, filtering for those with a confidence score greater than or equal to 0.4 (Marx and Fuegi, 2022). Second, we performed a similar extraction, restricted to articles tagged as "Environmental science" in MAG, following the same procedure used to identify environment-related scientific publications. For both datasets, citations were matched to European green patents from REGPAT. Articles are counted by patent, region, and priority year of the patent, and then aggregated at the regional-year level.

¹⁶ This accounts for approximately 5% of the observations. For a visualizations of the NUTS-2 regions where this correction was applied, see [Appendix 1](#).

¹⁷ Further details on patent-to-paper citation data from the Reliance on Science project can be found online: <https://relianceonscience.org/patent-to-paper-citations>.

4. Methodology

Section 4. presents the methodology of the paper, divided into four subsections. The first, [Section 4.1.](#) presents the empirical model, while the second, [Section 4.2.](#), introduces the explanatory variables. [Section 4.3.](#) describes the control variables. [Section 4.4.](#) outline the approach used to examine temporal dynamics.

4.1. Empirical model

We employ an econometric approach to examine the effect of green patents, as well as regional technological and scientific capabilities, on economic and environmental productivity in European regions over time. Specifically, we estimate a fixed-effects (FE) model that accounts for longitudinal data spanning 2000 to 2019 across 221 European regions in 25 countries. Standard errors are Driscoll-Kraay robust, correcting for heteroskedasticity, autocorrelation, and cross-sectional dependence ([Driscoll and Kraay, 1998](#)). As a robustness check, we re-estimate models with standard errors clustered at the country level to account for potential within-country correlation. We also replace year fixed effects with a binary indicator for the post-2008 financial crisis period—given its likely adverse impact on labour productivity, which is measured relative to total employment. This specification allows us to test for a structural shift in productivity following the crisis. Overall, the direction and magnitude of our main coefficients remain consistent across specifications.

Environmental productivity (EP), one of the two dependent variables, is measured as the annual ratio of GDP to total GHG emissions (in kilotonnes of CO₂-equivalents) at the regional level, where r and t denote region and time period respectively:¹⁸

$$EP_{r,t} = \frac{GDP_{r,t}}{Emissions_{r,t}}$$

Economic productivity, the second dependent variable, is proxied by labour productivity (LP), defined as the annual ratio of GDP to the total number of employees in the region:

$$LP_{r,t} = \frac{GDP_{r,t}}{Employees_{r,t}}$$

¹⁸ Total GHG emissions are extracted from the EDGAR dataset (JRC). GDP is obtained from Eurostat in current euro prices and adjusted using the national average Harmonised Index of Consumer Prices (HICP, 2015=100).

As EP and LP are constructed as ratios of GDP to GHG emissions and total employment, respectively, higher values of these indicators reflect better environmental or labour performance of that region—indicating that less GHG emissions or fewer employees are required to generate a given level of GDP.

The set of explanatory variables includes green technological patents (H.1/1.bis); regional capabilities—technological, green technological, and environmental scientific knowledge (H.2/3/4); and the interaction between regional capabilities and green patents (H2.bis/3.bis/4.bis). The main FE regression is specified as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \log(Y_{r,t}) = & \beta_0 + \beta_1 \operatorname{asinh}(\operatorname{GP}_{r,t-1}) + \theta_1 \operatorname{rank}(\operatorname{ECI}_{r,t-1}) \\ & + \theta_2 \operatorname{rank}(\operatorname{GCI}_{r,t-1}) + \beta_2 \operatorname{asinh}(\operatorname{EnvScience}_{r,t-1}) \\ & + \beta_3 \log(\operatorname{PopDensity}_{r,t-1}) + \beta_4 \operatorname{Education}_{r,t-1} \\ & + \beta_5 \log(\operatorname{R\&D}_{r,t-1}) + \gamma_r + \delta_t + \varepsilon_{r,t} \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

Where $Y_{r,t} \in \operatorname{EP}_{r,t}, \operatorname{LP}_{r,t}$ is the dependent variable—environmental productivity (EP) or labour productivity (LP)—in region r and year t , in logarithmic form. γ_r and δ_t denote region and year fixed effects, respectively. $\varepsilon_{r,t}$ is the error term.

We apply the inverse hyperbolic sine transformation (asinh) to green patent (GP) and environment-related scientific publication ($\operatorname{EnvScience}$) counts to address skewness and the high concentration of near-zero values in their distributions. All variables are regionally classified according to the NUTS 2021 framework to ensure temporal consistency. All covariates are lagged by one year to mitigate the possibility of simultaneity or reverse causality bias.¹⁹

We also estimate interaction models to investigate potential complementarities between regional capabilities and GTs in shaping both productivity outcomes.

¹⁹ Lagging covariates by one year ensures that the values of the covariates precede the dependent variable in time. This temporal ordering reduces the risk that the dependent variable influences the covariates (reverse causality) or that both are determined simultaneously within the same period.

4.2. Explanatory Variables

Table 4.1. Summary of explanatory variables

Type & Source	Variable name & Measurement	Description
Time-varying (PATSTAT)	GT → asinh(green patent count)	Count of green patents per 100,000 inhabitants in European NUTS-2 regions
	Tech. capabilities → rank(economic complexity)	Inverted regional ranking based on global technological capabilities
	Green tech. capabilities → rank(green complexity)	Inverted regional ranking based on global green cumulative technological capabilities
Time-varying (OpenAlex)	Environm. scientific capabilities → asinh(environm. scientific production)	Count of environment-related scientific publications per 10,000 inhabitants in European NUTS-2 regions

Green patent count is defined as the number of patents per 100,000 inhabitants that include at least one green-related CPC classification code, i.e., those within the Y02 or Y04S classes (Veefkind et al., 2012). To account for potential gaps in annual patent data, a 3-year backward averaged rolling window ($t - 2$ to t) is applied. For interpretability, the inverse hyperbolic sine (asinh) transformation is applied.

The economic complexity index (ECI), which refers to the regional technological capabilities, is measured using the Complexity-Fitness Method (CFM - Tacchella et al., 2012).²⁰ In brief, the CFM is an iterative non-linear algorithm that simultaneously considers regional fitness and

²⁰ The Complexity-Fitness Method (CFM) is a widely adopted and robust alternative to the original Method of Reflections (MoR - Hidalgo and Hausmann, 2009). The MoR has been criticized for defining technological complexity as a linear average of the locations producing a given technology, which tends to overvalue under-represented locations and technologies rather than those that are intrinsically more complex (e.g., Cristelli et al., 2013; Tacchella et al., 2012). The CFM addresses this by applying a non-linear approach that corrects for extreme distortions, giving greater weight to low-fitness locations when estimating technological complexity (Tacchella et al., 2012). As a result, the method highlights exclusive, highly complex technologies, particularly for locations with diverse and advanced technological capabilities (Caldarola et al., 2024).

technological sophistication, allowing them to mutually reinforce one another. Technologies are deemed more sophisticated only if they are specialized by a few regions with relatively high fitness—i.e., regions with a diversified set of technological specializations weighted by high sophistication scores.²¹ To account for potential gaps in annual patent data, a 3-year backward averaged rolling window ($t - 2$ to t) is applied. From this CFM, we use the region’s fitness score as a proxy for region-specific technological capabilities, taking into account the global landscape of regional technological specializations. However, since the process relies on independent matrices that evolve over time, the absolute magnitudes of these fitness scores are not directly comparable across regions or years. To address this issue, we adopt globally ranked complexity values, as recommended by [Caldarola et al. \(2024\)](#). For interpretative clarity, the ranking are reversed—regions with the lowest fitness are assigned the highest (i.e., first) ranks each year, and highest fitness are assigned the lowest (i.e., last) ranks each year. In addition, we standardized these ranks by subtracting their mean values and dividing the result by the standard deviation. This ensures a mean of zero, with a region ranked one corresponding to a value of one standard deviation above the mean.

The green complexity index (GCI), which captures cumulative regional technological capabilities in GTs, is also measured via the Complexity-Fitness Method (CFM) iterative algorithm process. The key methodological difference lies in how GC_i is computed differently from the original regional fitness score:²²

$$GC_i = \mathcal{P} \sum_{k \in \mathcal{G}} \rho_k^i Q_k^n \quad (1)$$

Where ρ_k^i is a dummy equal to 1 if region i is specialized in green technology k , and Q_k^n represents the sophistication of technology k , obtained from the CFM after n iterations. The index sums the sophistication of GTs in which a region is specialized, thus identifying regions with the strongest absolute capabilities in complex GTs.²³ For similar reasons as with the ECI, we apply a globally reversed ranking. Finally, the ranked scores are standardized by subtracting the mean and dividing by the standard deviation, which notably helps reduce potential correlation with ECI.

²¹ For a detailed description of the CFM applied in our case study, see [Appendix 2.a](#). As a robustness check, we construct an alternative measure of economic complexity using the Method of Reflections following a similar approach, see [Appendix 2.b](#).

²² As a robustness check, we construct an alternative measure of green economic complexity by applying the CFM filtering to GTs prior to computation. We follow the same normalization procedure as used for the GCI.

²³ Regional technological specialization is measured using the binary Revealed Technological Advantage (RTA), as detailed in [Appendix 2.a](#). This approach is widely adopted—notably in the Economic Complexity framework—due to its robustness with low patent counts, where continuous RTA tend to be unstable and noisy (e.g. [Balland et al., 2019](#)).

The environment-related scientific production, which captures the environment-related scientific capabilities, is measured by the count of environmental scientific publications per 10,000 inhabitants as extracted from OpenAlex in the [Data section](#). For interpretability, the inverse hyperbolic sine (asinh) transformation is applied.

4.3. Control variables

Table 4.2. Summary of control variables

Type & Source	Variable name & Measurement	Description
Time-varying (Eurostat)	log(Population density)	Total population per square kilometer on the total land area in European NUTS-2 regions
	Education rate	Share of the population aged 25–64 with tertiary education in European NUTS-2 regions
	log(R&D intensity)	Gross domestic expenditure on R&D in PPS per capita (2005 constant prices) in European NUTS-2 regions

To address potential omitted variable bias, we include time-varying regional controls and account for region and years fixed effects, which may influence the environmental or labour productivity of European regions. The three time-varying controls are extracted from the Eurostat database.²⁴ Population density is defined as the ratio of the total population in the NUTS-2 region to its total land area in square kilometres (as defined in 2018). Population density is expected to influence productivity outcomes through agglomeration effects that are associated with urban areas (e.g., better infrastructure, or larger markets, [Boschma et al., 2015](#); [Buendía Azorín and Sánchez de la Vega, 2015](#)). Human capital is proxied by education rate, measured as the ratio of the population aged 25–64 with tertiary education (ISCED levels 5 to 8) to the total population aged 25–64 in the NUTS-2 region. We acknowledge that this education rate is a partial measure of human capital, as it reflect solely formal educational attainment and

²⁴ Data from Eurostat can be found online: ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/main/data/database.

excludes other dimensions such as skills acquired through experience or non-formal training. Nevertheless, it remains a widely accepted proxy, as education is a key channel through which individuals acquire the skills and knowledge relevant to economic activity (e.g., [Buendía Azorín and Sánchez de la Vega, 2015](#); [Fischer et al., 2009](#)). R&D intensity is defined as gross domestic expenditure on R&D per capita in Purchasing Power Standards (PPS), expressed in 2005 constant prices, at the European NUTS-2 regional level. PPS adjusts for cost-of-living differences across regions, per capita scaling accounts for differences in regional size, and constant prices remove the effects of inflation—thus allowing meaningful comparisons over time. Empirical evidence showed that R&D intensity provides a non-linear (inverted U-shape) relationship with labour productivity: moderate R&D investment enhances productivity, while excessive spending may reduce its effectiveness ([Coccia, 2018](#)). Finally, we simultaneously control for year and region fixed effects to capture unobserved, time-invariant characteristics specific to each level influencing the environmental or labour productivity.

4.4. Temporal dynamics methodology

To examine the temporal dynamics of the independent variables over short- to long-term horizons, we estimate a series of finite distributed lag (FDL) regressions in which multiple lags of each explanatory variable are included simultaneously:

$$\log(Y_{r,t}) = \alpha + \beta_0 x_{t-1} + \beta_1 x_{t-3} + \beta_2 x_{t-5} + \dots + \beta_q x_{t-q} + \theta_1 \log(\text{PopDensity}_{r,t-1}) + \theta_2 \text{Education}_{r,t-1} + \theta_3 \log(\text{R\&D}_{r,t-1}) + \gamma_r + \delta_t + \varepsilon_{r,t} \quad (2)$$

Where x_t is the focal independent variable, $\beta_0, \beta_1, \dots, \beta_q$ are the lag coefficients, and q is the maximum lag order. Lags begin at one year and are spaced at two-year intervals to mitigate multicollinearity while capturing both immediate and delayed effects. This approach to capturing dynamic effects is well established and suggested by [Greene \(1997\)](#). Although the main panel spans 2000–2019, we leverage historical data from 1990 onward to construct extended lags of up to ten years for the independent variables, without incurring substantial data loss.²⁵ To preserve sample size and ensure model interpretability, two criteria are applied. First, the lag structure for each explanatory variable is selected to retain at least two-thirds of the original sample size, balancing temporal granularity with degrees of freedom. Second, we use the sequential F-test, as suggested by [Greene \(1997\)](#), to assess whether the inclusion of additional lags significantly improves model fit.

Accordingly, given the differing temporal scopes and data distributions of our key explanatory

²⁵ While green patents and environment-related scientific publications are available for earlier years, both measures are scaled by regional population, which is consistently reported by Eurostat only from 1990 onwards.

variables, we adopt variable-specific lag structures (q): green patents are lagged up to 9 years; green-specific cumulative complexity, economic complexity, and environment-related scientific production up to 15 years. To assess long-run effects, we compute cumulative effect of each explanatory variable by summing its lagged coefficients (e.g., Lanoie et al., 2008).²⁶

5. Main results

Section 5. presents the main results of the paper, divided into three subsections. The first, Section 5.1. present the descriptive statistics of variables, while the second Section 5.2., outlines the econometric results for both economic and environmental productivity. Finally, Section 5.3. reports the robustness checks.

5.1. Descriptive statistics

Figure 5.2. Green patent and environmental scientific article counts in NUTS-2 European regions (1990-2019)

²⁶ The corresponding distributed lag regressions are reported in Appendix 4.

As shown in Figure 5.2, both green patents and environmental scientific publications exhibit a substantial upward trend across European NUTS-2 regions from 1990 to 2019. Contrary to expectations under a linear science-to-technology model, green patenting accelerated earlier and more sharply than scientific production—particularly in the early 2000s and up to 2012. This pattern may be specific to GTs and likely reflects the influence of environmental regulation driven by the European Commission, particularly through directives aimed at spurring their development and adoption. In contrast, scientific production in environmental fields began to rise more significantly from 2011 onward and has continued to grow, while green patenting has slightly declined in recent years, suggesting a potential decoupling between environmental science and GTs trajectories.

Figure 5.3. Citations of environmental and non-environmental related scientific articles by green patents in NUTS-2 European regions (1990-2019)

Figure 5.3 presents the evolution of patent-to-article citations by green patents in NUTS-2 European regions between 1990 and 2019, distinguishing between environmental and non-environmental scientific publications. While absolute counts of citations to environmental scientific production are less prominent than non-environmental ones, they have steadily increased since the early 2000s and have followed a stronger growth trajectory than non-environmental citations, particularly around 2008. In contrast, citations to non-environmental articles have gradually declined since 2006. These trends suggest a growing alignment between green technological development and environmental scientific research in Europe, especially in the post-2010 period.

Figure 5.4. Citations of non-environmental related scientific articles by green patents in NUTS-2 European regions (Average 1990–2019)

Figure 5.5. Citations of environmental related scientific articles by green patents in NUTS-2 European regions (Average 1990–2019)

Statistic	Value	Interpretation
Pearson correlation	0.502	Moderate positive correlation, significant ($p < 2.2 \times 10^{-16}$)

Figures 5.4 and 5.5 map the spatial distribution of scientific citations by green patents across European NUTS-2 regions, averaged over the 1990-2019 period. The maps show that green patents in Europe draw not only environmental science, but also on a broader range of scientific fields (e.g., engineering, physics). The moderate positive correlation between environmental and non-environmental citations suggests complementarity rather than substitution in the knowledge base of GTs. Regional differences highlight the heterogeneity in how scientific knowledge is embedded in GTs, as well as varying degrees of integration of environmental science into regional green innovations.

Table 5.1. Descriptive statistics of variables (1990-2019)

Variable	Mean		SD		Min		Max	
	< 2005	≥ 2005	< 2005	≥ 2005	< 2005	≥ 2005	< 2005	≥ 2005
Environmental productivity (GDP/GHG)	2.74	3.37	2.03	2.77	0.17	0.16	16.58	20.95
Labour productivity (GDP/employees)	58.80	61.01	21.22	21.98	8.72	9.12	186.64	192.17
Green patent count	20.00	49.84	33.52	82.05	1	1	356.67	719
Economic complexity (inverted rank)	254.94	302.98	130.75	139.18	1	1	507	537
Green complexity (inverted rank)	180.47	241.32	104.13	127.55	1	1	414	502
Environmental publication count	56.40	240.61	97.32	389.77	1	1	1538	5718
Education rate (tertiary education)	0.18	0.26	0.07	0.09	0.05	0.07	0.46	0.58
Population density (Pop/Total area)	280.28	280.19	631.96	668.03	3.10	3.09	6210.55	7548.39
R&D intensity (PPS per capita, €)	301.55	413.07	318.19	434.12	4.63	4.78	2771.56	3082.44

Table 5.1 presents summary statistics for European NUTS-2 regions, split into symmetric 15-years periods before and after 2005. The post-2005 period shows higher mean values across most variables—particularly in green patenting, environmental scientific publications, and indicators of technological and green technological capabilities. These pattern shifts suggest an overall intensification of green innovation and environment-related scientific activity, coinciding with increased R&D intensity and higher education rates. The rise in economic and green complexity ranks also reflects strengthening technological and green technological capabilities across European regions relative to the global landscape. Additionally, the superior variance in green innovation-related and environmental publication metrics points to growing European regional disparities in green transition dynamics.

Figure 5.6. Environmental Productivity
(Average 2000–2019)

Figure 5.7. Labour Productivity
(Average 2000–2019)

Statistic	Value	Interpretation
Pearson correlation	0.593	Moderate positive correlation, significant ($p < 2.2 \times 10^{-16}$)

Figures 5.6 and 5.7 map the average levels of environmental productivity (GDP per unit of GHG emissions in kilotonnes of CO₂-equivalents) and labour productivity (GDP per employee) across European NUTS-2 regions between 2000 and 2019. While both indicators reveal strong regional concentrations, their spatial patterns only partially overlap. Labour productivity is notably higher in Central and Western European regions—particularly in parts of Belgium, across Germany, sections of the Netherlands, and Northern Italy. In contrast, environmental productivity is more prominent in southern Nordic regions and several areas of Eastern Europe. Capital regions tend to exhibit high values for both indicators. The Pearson correlation test indicates a moderate positive relationship between the two variables across regions. This suggests that while environmental and labour productivity tend to move together to some extent, they are not fully aligned—highlighting that environmental and economic productivity are shaped by distinct regional dynamics. This divergence reinforces the need to analyze them as complementary but distinct productivity metrics in the pursuit of economic and environmental sustainable growth.

Figure 5.8. Economic Complexity
(Average inverted rank 2000-2019)

Figure 5.9. Green Complexity
(Average inverted rank 2000-2019)

Statistic	Value	Interpretation
Spearman's rho	0.572	Moderate positive rank correlation, significant ($p < 2.2 \times 10^{-16}$)

Figures 5.8 and 5.9 map the average ranks of economic and green complexity—reflecting underlying technological and green technological capabilities—across NUTS-2 regions between 2000 and 2019. Both maps reveal a strong concentration of technological capabilities in Western and Northern Europe, though with notable differences depending on the metric. Technological capabilities are particularly concentrated in Germany and more broadly across Central Europe. In contrast, green technological capabilities (Figure 5.9) displays a broader geographic distribution, with stronger concentrations in the Nordic countries and parts of the United Kingdom. This suggests that green technological capabilities are more evenly spread across Europe, potentially reflecting recent policy-driven innovation efforts. The Spearman rank correlation test indicates a moderate positive relationship between the two variables across regions, supporting the view that both EC metrics capture related but distinct dimensions and should be analyzed independently yet complementarily.

Figure 5.10. Economic complexity ranking in NUTS-2 European regions (2000-2019)
(The labeled region per country corresponds to the one with the highest GDP, typically simplified to its main economic city)

Figure 5.11. Green complexity ranking in NUTS-2 European regions (2000-2019)
 (The labeled region per country corresponds to the one with the highest GDP, typically simplified to its main economic city)

Figures 5.10 and 5.11 illustrate the evolution of complexity rankings across European NUTS-2 regions. For visualization purposes, only the region with the highest average GDP per country over the 2000-2019 period is labeled, and most region names are simplified to reflect their main economic city. The economic complexity rankings (Figure 5.10) show a relatively stable hierarchy, with regions such as Milan, Zurich, Paris and Munich consistently maintaining top positions throughout the period. At the lower end of the distribution, several Eastern and Southern European regions—including Zagreb, Riga, and Bratislava—persistently occupy weaker positions, suggesting lower accumulation of technological capabilities. This general temporal stability reflects the path-dependent nature of economic complexity: regions with historically embedded technological capabilities tend to maintain their technological advantage, underscoring spatial inequalities in Europe (e.g., Pinheiro et al., 2022)

In contrast, the green complexity rankings (Figure 5.11) appear more dynamic, with notable up-

ward mobility observed in some Eastern and Southern European regions, including Budapest, Ljubljana, and Bucharest. However, these descriptive results should be interpreted with caution as they are based only on green technological patent classes, and some regions may have a limited number of green patents. Overall, comparing both graphs reveals that regions with the most advanced technological capabilities are not necessarily those that possess a green technological orientation. This distinction highlights the importance of analyzing both economic and green complexity to fully apprehend the role of local technological capabilities in shaping productivity trajectories.

5.2. Econometric results

As outlined in our main hypotheses, GTs are expected to significantly enhance EP. Regarding LP, GTs are hypothesised to exert an effect that may be either negative or positive. In addition, regional technological and scientific capabilities—particularly those related to GTs and environmental science—as well as their interaction with GTs, are expected to have a positive direct and mediated effect on both economic and environmental productivity.

As stated in the [Methodology section](#), we tested these hypotheses using econometric estimations that control for potential confounders, as well as region and year fixed effects. The lag structure, based on two-year intervals for each independent variable, is each time designed to retain at least three-quarters of the original sample size.

Table 5.2 presents the estimated direct effects of GT on EP and LP, in line with hypotheses H1 and H1.bis. Column (1) to (4) report the direct effect of GTs on EP, with stepwise inclusion of confounders. Column (5) to (8) report the corresponding effects on LP. The coefficient of interest, green patents (GPs), shows a positive and statistically significant direct effect on both EP and LP outcomes at the 99% confidence level (column (4) and (8)).²⁷

Figure 5.12 and 5.13 display the Cumulative effects of GPs on EP and LP.²⁸ For EP, the cumulative effect rises steadily, with 95% confidence intervals consistently above zero from $t - 3$, confirming strong and persistent environmental returns to green innovation. Specifically, a 1% increase in the count of GPs per 100,000 inhabitants is associated with a 8% cumulative increase in EP over the following 9 years at the 95% confidence level.

In contrast, the cumulative effect on LP is smaller and less precisely estimated, with wider con-

²⁷ The inverse hyperbolic sine (asinh) transformation approximates the natural logarithm, allowing for elasticity-like interpretations, while performing better with zero or small values. See [Bellemare and Wichman \(2020\)](#) for a detailed discussion.

²⁸ These cumulative effects are derived from the distributed lag regressions reported in [Appendix 4.a](#).

confidence intervals that approach zero around mid-lags—indicating weaker and more uncertain long-run gains in LP. Specifically, a 1% increase in the count of GPs per 100,000 inhabitants is associated with a 3.9% cumulative increase in LP over the following 9 years at the 95% confidence level.

Table 5.2. Fixed effects estimates: impact of green technology

	<i>log</i> (Environmental Productivity)				<i>log</i> (Labour Productivity)			
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)	(8)
<i>asinh</i> (GP _{<i>r,t-1</i>})	0.014*** <i>p</i> = 0.000	0.014*** <i>p</i> = 0.000	0.016*** <i>p</i> = 0.000	0.018*** <i>p</i> = 0.000	0.031** <i>p</i> = 0.021	0.031** <i>p</i> = 0.018	0.018*** <i>p</i> = 0.005	0.019*** <i>p</i> = 0.002
Education _{<i>r,t-1</i>}		0.186 <i>p</i> = 0.123	0.161 <i>p</i> = 0.166	0.147 <i>p</i> = 0.217		0.106 <i>p</i> = 0.180	0.285*** <i>p</i> = 0.007	0.275*** <i>p</i> = 0.008
<i>log</i> (PopDensity _{<i>r,t-1</i>})			0.087* <i>p</i> = 0.071	0.102** <i>p</i> = 0.042			-0.617*** <i>p</i> = 0.000	-0.607*** <i>p</i> = 0.001
<i>log</i> (R&DIntensity _{<i>r,t-1</i>})				0.032*** <i>p</i> = 0.000				0.023** <i>p</i> = 0.048
Adjusted R ²	0.981	0.981	0.981	0.981	0.939	0.939	0.949	0.950
Region FE	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Year FE	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Observations	2,901	2,901	2,901	2,901	2,901	2,901	2,901	2,901

Note: Robust Driscoll-Kraay SEs. **p*<0.1, ***p*<0.05, ****p*<0.01

Figure 5.12. Cumulative effect of GPs on EP (up to *t-9*, 95% CIs)

Figure 5.13. Cumulative effect of GPs on LP (up to *t-9*, 95% CIs)

Table 5.3 presents the estimated effects of regional capabilities on productivity, testing hypotheses H2, H3 and H4. Capabilities are measured using the Economic Complexity Index (ECI) for general technological capabilities, the Green Complexity Index (GCI) for green-specific cumulative capabilities, and the count of environment-related scientific publications (EnvScience) for

environmental scientific capabilities. Columns (1)–(3) report direct effects on EP, while columns (5)–(7) present results for LP. To account for potential non-linearities in the effect of environmental scientific capabilities, we include a quadratic term in columns (4) and (8) for EP and LP, respectively.

The ECI shows no significant direct effect on EP (column (1)), but a positive and statistically significant direct effect on LP (column (5)) at the 95% confidence level. These findings suggest that ECI directly influences LP, but not EP. In contrast, GCI does not show significant direct effects on EP or LP (columns (2) and (6)). The results show a positive and statistically significant direct effect of EnvScience on EP at the 99% confidence level (column (3)), while no significant direct effect is observed for LP (columns (7)). When including a quadratic term for EnvScience (columns (4) and (8)), the results indicate a U-shape relationship with both productivity outcomes. This implies that the contribution of environmental scientific capabilities to productivity is non-linear: such capabilities begin to exert positive effects only beyond a certain intensity—particularly for EP, where the magnitude of the effect is stronger.

Figures 5.14 and 5.15 show the Cumulative effects of ECI on EP and LP.²⁹ A delayed effect of ECI on EP is observed, the cumulative effect increases steadily across the entire time horizon, with 95% confidence intervals above zero from the second cumulated year—indicating persistent and significant long-run environmental returns. For LP, the cumulative effect grows more strongly, with a tighter confidence band, confirming broad and sustained economic benefits of technological complexity. Specifically, a one standard deviation increase in the rank of economic complexity is associated with a 8.62% cumulative increase in EP, or a 12.12% cumulative increase in LP over the following 15 years at the 95% confidence level. Hence, ECI shows a direct effect on LP and a delayed effect on EP, with both productivity outcomes affected over the medium and long term, supporting H2.

Figures 5.16 and 5.17 plot the cumulative effects of GCI.³⁰ GCI has a significant cumulative effect on both productivity outcomes in the medium term, with a more consistently positive and statistically significant long-run effect on LP than on EP. The effect on EP is smaller and less robust, with wide confidence intervals that include zero. The results outline a more indirect effect of green-specific cumulative technological capabilities on productivity gains, partially supporting H3.

Figures 5.18 and 5.19 display the Cumulative effects of EnvScience on EP and LP.³¹ For EP, the cumulative effect initially rises, but dips around the mid-horizon (years 5–10), with confidence

²⁹ The corresponding distributed lag regressions are reported in [Appendix 4.b](#).

³⁰ The corresponding distributed lag regressions are reported in [Appendix 4.c](#).

³¹ The corresponding distributed lag regressions are reported in [Appendix 4.d](#).

intervals temporarily crossing zero—before becoming statistically significant again toward the end of the time window (year 15). This pattern points to highly delayed environmental benefits: a 1% increase in the count of environment-related scientific publications per 10,000 inhabitants fifteen year prior is associated with a 4.51% cumulative increase in EP at the 95% confidence level. For LP, the cumulative effect rises modestly in the early years, but flattens and declines in the long run, with confidence intervals broadening and overlapping zero beyond year 8. This suggests limited and statistically fragile productivity gains from scientific output in the labour dimension. The overall econometric evidence suggests that environment-related scientific capabilities have a positive impact on EP, exerting both a direct and a substantially delayed long-term effect, while their relationship with LP appears less direct and more uncertain.

The results confirm that general technological capabilities enhance both productivity outcomes, with immediate effects on LP and delayed effects on EP, both also showing long-term productivity gains. In contrast, green-specific cumulative capabilities primarily support both productivity outcomes in the medium (LP) or long term (EP), without robust evidence of broader productivity gains. Finally, environment-related scientific capabilities positively influence both outcomes, with a direct and substantially delayed effect on EP, and a short, medium-term effect on LP.

The positive and direct effect of EnvScience on EP may reflect increased European attention to environmental issues in recent years, potentially linked to the growing emergence of environment-related scientific publications. Table 5.4 presents the estimated direct effects of regional scientific capabilities on productivity outcomes, with the analysis split into two equal periods: 2000–2009 and 2010–2019. Columns (1)–(2) report direct effects on EP for each period, while columns (3)–(4) present the corresponding results for LP. EnvScience has no significant direct effect on EP in the pre-2010 period (column (1)), but exhibits a positive and statistically significant effect in the post-2010 period (column (2)), at the 99% confidence level. No significant direct effect is observed for LP in either period (columns 3–4). These results support the view that the increase salience of environmental issues in Europe, alongside a rise in related scientific output, may help explain the more recent short-term positive relationship between EnvScience and EP.

Table 5.3. Fixed effects estimates: impact of regional capabilities

	<i>log</i> (Environmental Productivity)				<i>log</i> (Labour Productivity)			
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)	(8)
<i>rank</i> (<i>ECl</i> _{<i>r,t-1</i>})	0.007				0.019**			
	<i>p</i> = 0.448				<i>p</i> = 0.027			
<i>rank</i> (<i>GCl</i> _{<i>r,t-1</i>})		0.001				0.003		
		<i>p</i> = 0.848				<i>p</i> = 0.159		
<i>asinh</i> (<i>EnvScience</i> _{<i>r,t-1</i>})			0.043***	-0.077**			0.021	-0.011
			<i>p</i> = 0.001	<i>p</i> = 0.013			<i>p</i> = 0.102	<i>p</i> = 0.576
Quadratic[<i>asinh</i> (<i>EnvScience</i> _{<i>r,t-1</i>})]				0.047***				0.013**
				<i>p</i> = 0.000				<i>p</i> = 0.017
<i>asinh</i> (<i>GP</i> _{<i>r,t-1</i>})	0.009**	0.010**	0.009*	-0.001	0.013**	0.015**	0.014**	0.011*
	<i>p</i> = 0.042	<i>p</i> = 0.023	<i>p</i> = 0.055	<i>p</i> = 0.843	<i>p</i> = 0.035	<i>p</i> = 0.020	<i>p</i> = 0.032	<i>p</i> = 0.068
Education _{<i>r,t-1</i>}	0.205*	0.210*	0.147	0.064	0.281***	0.289***	0.267***	0.245**
	<i>p</i> = 0.097	<i>p</i> = 0.077	<i>p</i> = 0.171	<i>p</i> = 0.585	<i>p</i> = 0.007	<i>p</i> = 0.006	<i>p</i> = 0.005	<i>p</i> = 0.011
<i>log</i> (<i>PopDensity</i> _{<i>r,t-1</i>})	0.088*	0.088**	0.089**	0.070*	-0.618***	-0.616***	-0.615***	-0.620***
	<i>p</i> = 0.057	<i>p</i> = 0.046	<i>p</i> = 0.044	<i>p</i> = 0.090	<i>p</i> = 0.001	<i>p</i> = 0.001	<i>p</i> = 0.001	<i>p</i> = 0.001
<i>log</i> (<i>R&DIntensity</i> _{<i>r,t-1</i>})	0.033***	0.033***	0.033***	0.038***	0.026**	0.028**	0.028**	0.029**
	<i>p</i> = 0.000	<i>p</i> = 0.000	<i>p</i> = 0.000	<i>p</i> = 0.000	<i>p</i> = 0.033	<i>p</i> = 0.023	<i>p</i> = 0.027	<i>p</i> = 0.020
Adjusted <i>R</i> ²	0.982	0.982	0.982	0.982	0.951	0.951	0.951	0.951
Region FE	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Year FE	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Observations	2,800	2,800	2,800	2,800	2,800	2,800	2,800	2,800

Note: Robust Driscoll-Kraay SEs. **p*<0.1; ***p*<0.05; ****p*<0.01

Figure 5.14. Cumulative effect of ECI on EP (up to t-15, 95% CIs)

Figure 5.15. Cumulative effect of ECI on LP (up to t-15, 95% CIs)

Figure 5.16. Cumulative effect of GCI on EP (up to t-15, 95% CIs)

Figure 5.17. Cumulative effect of GCI on LP (up to t-15, 95% CIs)

Figure 5.18. Cumulative effect of EnvScience on EP (up to t-15, 95% CIs)

Figure 5.19. Cumulative effect of EnvScience on LP (up to t-15, 95% CIs)

Table 5.4. Fixed effects estimates: impact of regional scientific capabilities (split into two equal periods)

	log(Environmental Productivity)		log(Labour Productivity)	
	≤ 2009	> 2009	≤ 2009	> 2009
$asinh(EnvScience_{r,t-1})$	0.026 $p = 0.372$	0.049*** $p = 0.002$	0.017 $p = 0.197$	-0.013 $p = 0.382$
$asinh(GP_{r,t-1})$	-0.006 $p = 0.470$	-0.001 $p = 0.889$	-0.004 $p = 0.611$	0.012 $p = 0.544$
Education $_{r,t-1}$	-0.241** $p = 0.044$	-0.087 $p = 0.490$	0.020 $p = 0.807$	0.050 $p = 0.673$
$log(PopDensity_{r,t-1})$	-0.240* $p = 0.100$	0.040*** $p = 0.002$	-0.218 $p = 0.266$	-0.576** $p = 0.023$
$log(R\&DIntensity_{r,t-1})$	0.002 $p = 0.921$	0.016* $p = 0.054$	0.019* $p = 0.061$	0.013 $p = 0.250$
Adjusted R ²	0.988	0.988	0.980	0.952
Region FE	✓	✓	✓	✓
Year FE	✓	✓	✓	✓
Observations	1,230	1,521	1,230	1,521

Note: Robust Driscoll-Kraay SEs. * $p < 0.1$; ** $p < 0.05$; *** $p < 0.01$

Table 5.5 reports the results for the estimated combined effects of GTs, measured by GPs, with regional capabilities on EP and LP, and serves to test hypotheses H2.bis, H3.bis, and H4.bis. Column (1) presents the interaction effect between GPs and ECI on EP; column (2) reports the interaction effect between GPs and GCI on EP; column (3) reports the interaction effect of GPs and EnvScience on EP. Columns (4) to (6) follow the same structure for LP.

The interaction term between GTs and technological capabilities is positive and statistically significant for EP at the 95% confidence level (column (1)), but not significant for LP (column (4)). The interaction between GTs and green-specific cumulative technological capabilities is also positive and highly significant for EP at the 99% confidence level (column (2)), but remains insignificant for LP (column (5)). Similarly, the interaction between GTs and environment-related

scientific capabilities is positive and strongly significant for EP at the 99% confidence level (column (3)), with no effect observed for LP (column (6)).

The overall econometric evidence suggests that the effectiveness of GTs in enhancing productivity is mediated by regional capabilities, particularly technological and environment-related scientific, but these effects are limited to EP. Specifically, a 1% increase in the count of green patents per 100,000 inhabitants, combined with a one standard deviation increase in the rank of economic complexity one year prior is associated with a 2.1% increase in EP. Similarly, a 1% increase in the count of green patents per 100,000 inhabitants, combined with a 1% increase in the count of environment-related scientific publications per 10,000 inhabitants, one year prior is associated with a 2.5% increase in EP at the 99% confidence level. These findings support the view that the environmental returns to green innovation are significantly enhanced in regions with stronger technological or environment-related scientific capabilities, while no comparable productivity gains are observed for labour productivity.

Table 5.5. Fixed effects estimates: impact of green technology combined with regional capabilities

	<i>log</i> (Environmental Productivity)			<i>log</i> (Labour Productivity)		
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)
<i>asinh</i> ($GP_{r,t-1}$) × <i>rank</i> ($ECl_{r,t-1}$)	0.021** <i>p</i> = 0.025			-0.009 <i>p</i> = 0.284		
<i>asinh</i> ($GP_{r,t-1}$) × <i>rank</i> ($GCl_{r,t-1}$)		0.011*** <i>p</i> = 0.0002			0.0004 <i>p</i> = 0.823	
<i>asinh</i> ($GP_{r,t-1}$) × <i>asinh</i> ($EnvScience_{r,t-1}$)			0.025*** <i>p</i> = 0.001			-0.003 <i>p</i> = 0.748
<i>rank</i> ($ECl_{r,t-1}$)	-0.010 <i>p</i> = 0.271			0.026** <i>p</i> = 0.028		
<i>rank</i> ($GCl_{r,t-1}$)		-0.013** <i>p</i> = 0.012			0.002 <i>p</i> = 0.456	
<i>asinh</i> ($EnvScience_{r,t-1}$)			0.006 <i>p</i> = 0.770			0.025 <i>p</i> = 0.177
<i>asinh</i> ($GP_{r,t-1}$)	-0.009 <i>p</i> = 0.388	0.006 <i>p</i> = 0.237	-0.019* <i>p</i> = 0.052	0.021** <i>p</i> = 0.013	0.015** <i>p</i> = 0.023	0.017* <i>p</i> = 0.093
Education $_{r,t-1}$	0.239** <i>p</i> = 0.035	0.217* <i>p</i> = 0.063	0.179* <i>p</i> = 0.069	0.267*** <i>p</i> = 0.007	0.289*** <i>p</i> = 0.006	0.264*** <i>p</i> = 0.004
<i>log</i> (PopDensity $_{r,t-1}$)	0.080* <i>p</i> = 0.089	0.082* <i>p</i> = 0.056	0.067 <i>p</i> = 0.138	-0.614*** <i>p</i> = 0.001	-0.617*** <i>p</i> = 0.001	-0.612*** <i>p</i> = 0.001
<i>log</i> (R&DIntensity $_{r,t-1}$)	0.037*** <i>p</i> = 0.000	0.038*** <i>p</i> = 0.000	0.039*** <i>p</i> = 0.000	0.024** <i>p</i> = 0.048	0.028** <i>p</i> = 0.021	0.027** <i>p</i> = 0.034
Adjusted <i>R</i> ²	0.982	0.982	0.982	0.951	0.951	0.951
Region FE	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Year FE	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Obs.	2,800	2,800	2,800	2,800	2,800	2,800

Note: Robust Driscoll-Kraay SEs. **p*<0.1; ***p*<0.05; ****p*<0.01

5.3. Robustness checks

Table 5.6. Fixed effects estimates: impact of regional capabilities using (1) the Complexity-Reflections method for ECI, (2) Green ECI instead of GCI, and (3) EnvScience based on a keyword list

	log(Environmental Productivity)			log(Labour Productivity)		
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)
<i>rank</i> (ECI _{<i>r,t-1</i>})	0.005 <i>p</i> = 0.452			0.006 <i>p</i> = 0.174		
<i>rank</i> (GreenECI _{<i>r,t-1</i>})		-0.0002 <i>p</i> = 0.955			0.002 <i>p</i> = 0.204	
<i>rank</i> (EnvScience _{<i>r,t-1</i>})			0.038** <i>p</i> = 0.012			0.009 <i>p</i> = 0.353
<i>asinh</i> (GP _{<i>r,t-1</i>})	0.010** <i>p</i> = 0.029	0.010** <i>p</i> = 0.021	0.008* <i>p</i> = 0.069	0.013** <i>p</i> = 0.028	0.014** <i>p</i> = 0.024	0.013** <i>p</i> = 0.045
Education _{<i>r,t-1</i>}	0.205* <i>p</i> = 0.087	0.209* <i>p</i> = 0.075	0.150 <i>p</i> = 0.135	0.294*** <i>p</i> = 0.007	0.289*** <i>p</i> = 0.007	0.284*** <i>p</i> = 0.005
<i>log</i> (PopDensity _{<i>r,t-1</i>})	0.090* <i>p</i> = 0.052	0.091** <i>p</i> = 0.046	0.099** <i>p</i> = 0.043	-0.615*** <i>p</i> = 0.001	-0.616*** <i>p</i> = 0.001	-0.613*** <i>p</i> = 0.001
<i>log</i> (R&DIntensity _{<i>r,t-1</i>})	0.032*** <i>p</i> = 0.000	0.033*** <i>p</i> = 0.000	0.033*** <i>p</i> = 0.000	0.023** <i>p</i> = 0.040	0.024** <i>p</i> = 0.034	0.024** <i>p</i> = 0.039
Adjusted <i>R</i> ²	0.982	0.982	0.982	0.951	0.951	0.951
Region FE	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Year FE	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Observations	2,828	2,828	2,828	2,828	2,828	2,828

Note: Robust Driscoll-Kraay SEs. **p*<0.1; ***p*<0.05; ****p*<0.01

Figure 5.20. Cumulative effect of alternative ECI on EP (up to t-17, 95% CIs)

Figure 5.21. Cumulative effect of alternative ECI on LP (up to t-17, 95% CIs)

Figure 5.22. Cumulative effect of alternative Green ECI on EP (up to t-15, 95% CIs)

Figure 5.23. Cumulative effect of alternative Green ECI on LP (up to t-15, 95% CIs)

Figure 5.24. Cumulative effect of alternative EnvScience on EP (up to t-15, 95% CIs)

Figure 5.25. Cumulative effect of alternative EnvScience on LP (up to t-15, 95% CIs)

Table 5.7. Fixed effects estimates: impact of green technology using country-clustered robust standard errors

	log(Environmental Productivity)				log(Labour Productivity)			
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)	(8)
GP _{r,t-1}	0.008*** <i>p</i> = 0.009	0.008*** <i>p</i> = 0.008	0.008*** <i>p</i> = 0.008	0.009*** <i>p</i> = 0.007	0.004 <i>p</i> = 0.136	0.004 <i>p</i> = 0.141	0.003* <i>p</i> = 0.069	0.004** <i>p</i> = 0.037
Education _{r,t-1}		0.190 <i>p</i> = 0.573	0.166 <i>p</i> = 0.649	0.152 <i>p</i> = 0.668		0.108 <i>p</i> = 0.661	0.287* <i>p</i> = 0.062	0.278* <i>p</i> = 0.063
log(PopDensity _{r,t-1})			0.086 <i>p</i> = 0.330	0.100 <i>p</i> = 0.349			-0.621*** <i>p</i> = 0.000	-0.611*** <i>p</i> = 0.000
log(R&DIntensity _{r,t-1})				0.033** <i>p</i> = 0.017				0.023* <i>p</i> = 0.094
Adjusted R ²	0.981	0.981	0.981	0.981	0.939	0.939	0.949	0.950
Region FE	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Year FE	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Observations	2,901	2,901	2,901	2,901	2,901	2,901	2,901	2,901

Note: Robust Country-clustered SEs. **p*<0.1; ***p*<0.05; ****p*<0.01

Table 5.8. Fixed effects estimates: impact of regional capabilities using country-clustered robust standard errors

	<i>log</i> (Environmental Productivity)			<i>log</i> (Labour Productivity)		
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)
<i>rank</i> (<i>ECI</i> _{<i>r,t-1</i>})	0.008 <i>p</i> = 0.563			0.020 <i>p</i> = 0.118		
<i>rank</i> (<i>GCI</i> _{<i>r,t-1</i>})		0.001 <i>p</i> = 0.487			0.003 <i>p</i> = 0.124	
<i>asinh</i> (<i>EnvScience</i> _{<i>r,t-1</i>})			0.045* <i>p</i> = 0.075			0.022 <i>p</i> = 0.174
<i>GP</i> _{<i>r,t-1</i>}	0.007** <i>p</i> = 0.037	0.007** <i>p</i> = 0.028	0.007** <i>p</i> = 0.030	0.003* <i>p</i> = 0.090	0.003* <i>p</i> = 0.072	0.003* <i>p</i> = 0.069
<i>Education</i> _{<i>r,t-1</i>}	0.206 <i>p</i> = 0.499	0.208 <i>p</i> = 0.499	0.145 <i>p</i> = 0.596	0.283** <i>p</i> = 0.045	0.291** <i>p</i> = 0.044	0.268* <i>p</i> = 0.081
<i>log</i> (<i>PopDensity</i> _{<i>r,t-1</i>})	0.089 <i>p</i> = 0.250	0.089 <i>p</i> = 0.241	0.091 <i>p</i> = 0.148	-0.620*** <i>p</i> = 0.000	-0.620*** <i>p</i> = 0.000	-0.618*** <i>p</i> = 0.000
<i>log</i> (<i>R&DIntensity</i> _{<i>r,t-1</i>})	0.034** <i>p</i> = 0.013	0.035*** <i>p</i> = 0.010	0.035*** <i>p</i> = 0.007	0.026 <i>p</i> = 0.120	0.028* <i>p</i> = 0.085	0.028* <i>p</i> = 0.083
Adjusted R ²	0.982	0.982	0.982	0.951	0.951	0.951
Region FE	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Year FE	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Observations	2,800	2,800	2,800	2,800	2,800	2,800

Note: Robust Country-clustered SEs. **p*<0.1; ***p*<0.05; ****p*<0.01

Table 5.9. Fixed effects estimates: impact of green technology including a dummy for the 2008 crisis period

	<i>log</i> (Environmental Productivity)				<i>log</i> (Labour Productivity)			
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)	(8)
Crisis (Post-2008)	0.127*** <i>p</i> = 0.006	0.055** <i>p</i> = 0.042	0.054** <i>p</i> = 0.045	0.039* <i>p</i> = 0.086	-0.010 <i>p</i> = 0.429	-0.037*** <i>p</i> = 0.001	-0.025*** <i>p</i> = 0.000	-0.032*** <i>p</i> = 0.000
<i>asinh</i> (GP _{<i>r,t-1</i>})	0.082*** <i>p</i> = 0.008	0.036*** <i>p</i> = 0.006	0.037*** <i>p</i> = 0.005	0.036*** <i>p</i> = 0.003	0.040*** <i>p</i> = 0.0003	0.023*** <i>p</i> = 0.004	0.016** <i>p</i> = 0.033	0.015** <i>p</i> = 0.027
Education _{<i>r,t-1</i>}		1.634*** <i>p</i> = 0.000	1.630*** <i>p</i> = 0.000	1.414*** <i>p</i> = 0.000		0.611*** <i>p</i> = 0.000	0.741*** <i>p</i> = 0.000	0.648*** <i>p</i> = 0.000
<i>log</i> (PopDensity _{<i>r,t-1</i>})			0.021 <i>p</i> = 0.706	0.064 <i>p</i> = 0.254			-0.641*** <i>p</i> = 0.000	-0.623*** <i>p</i> = 0.001
<i>log</i> (R&DIntensity _{<i>r,t-1</i>})				0.090*** <i>p</i> = 0.000				0.039*** <i>p</i> = 0.000
Adjusted R ²	0.981	0.981	0.981	0.981	0.939	0.939	0.949	0.950
Region FE	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Year FE	×	×	×	×	×	×	×	×
Observations	2,901	2,901	2,901	2,901	2,901	2,901	2,901	2,901

Note: Robust Country-clustered SEs. **p*<0.1; ***p*<0.05; ****p*<0.01

Table 5.10. Fixed effects estimates: impact of regional capabilities including a dummy for the 2008 crisis period

	log(Environmental Productivity)			log(Labour Productivity)		
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)
Crisis (Post-2008)	0.042*	0.042*	0.028	-0.032***	-0.031***	-0.036***
	$p = 0.081$	$p = 0.078$	$p = 0.113$	$p = 0.000$	$p = 0.000$	$p = 0.000$
$rank(ECI_{r,t-1})$	0.006			0.018**		
	$p = 0.615$			$p = 0.038$		
$rank(GCI_{r,t-1})$		0.004			0.004*	
		$p = 0.292$			$p = 0.089$	
$asinh(EnvScience_{r,t-1})$			0.152***			0.051***
			$p = 0.000$			$p = 0.000$
$asinh(GP_{r,t-1})$	0.028**	0.029**	0.014	0.008	0.010	0.005
	$p = 0.012$	$p = 0.014$	$p = 0.180$	$p = 0.207$	$p = 0.119$	$p = 0.435$
Education $_{r,t-1}$	1.480***	1.468***	0.825***	0.665***	0.664***	0.460***
	$p = 0.000$	$p = 0.000$	$p = 0.000$	$p = 0.000$	$p = 0.000$	$p = 0.000$
$log(PopDensity_{r,t-1})$	0.051	0.050	0.063	-0.635***	-0.634***	-0.628***
	$p = 0.339$	$p = 0.325$	$p = 0.217$	$p = 0.001$	$p = 0.001$	$p = 0.001$
$log(R\&DIntensity_{r,t-1})$	0.094***	0.094***	0.074***	0.041***	0.043***	0.037***
	$p = 0.000$	$p = 0.000$	$p = 0.000$	$p = 0.000$	$p = 0.000$	$p = 0.003$
Adjusted R^2	0.982	0.982	0.982	0.951	0.951	0.951
Region FE	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Year FE	×	×	×	×	×	×
Observations	2,800	2,800	2,800	2,800	2,800	2,800

Note: Robust Driscoll-Kraay SEs. * $p < 0.1$; ** $p < 0.05$; *** $p < 0.01$

5.3.1. Limitations and future research avenues

Several avenues for future research remain. First, we rely on patent-based indicators to capture technological innovation and capabilities. While informative, these proxies may overlook non-patented, informal, or organizational innovation processes that are not reflected in patent data. Future research could explore alternative indicators, such as green products data or trademarks, to specifically capture GT adoption. Second, although we apply two approaches to identify environment-related scientific publications, there is no, to our knowledge, widely accepted strategy for robustly distinguishing such publications across disciplines. Further work is needed to refine these measures and assess their long-term effects on productivity. Notably, our analysis is limited to a 15-year lag structure for environment-related scientific capabilities, which may be insufficient given evidence that scientific impacts can take up to 20 years to materialize into productivity effects (Adams, 1990; Baldos et al., 2019). Third, our EP indicator—based on value added per unit of GHG emissions—does not capture broader ecological dimensions such as biodiversity loss or resource depletion. Moreover, it may misrepresent high-emission regions with high value-added creation as environmentally productive. Fourth, we acknowledge the potential for omitted variable bias. Including key elements of the policy mix for sustainability transitions (Rogge et al., 2017)—such as the comprehensiveness of the mix, the sequencing of policy implementation, and the design of policies—could help mitigate this bias. Fifth, while our models account for time lags and cumulative interpretation, multicollinearity among lagged terms remains a limitation. Future studies could address this by extending the temporal coverage or by applying distributed lag model specifications. Sixth, replicating this analysis at the firm or industry level (Ghisetti and Quatraro, 2017), or across finer spatial or non-European contexts, would offer valuable external validation. Finally, given the possibility that more productive regions may attract green patenting and R&D, concerns about reverse causality remain. While we partially address this by including fixed effects and lagged covariates to control for unobserved heterogeneity, we do not implement an instrumental variable approach—an avenue that future research could pursue to better address potential endogeneity.

6. Conclusion

This paper examined how green technologies (GTs) and regional capabilities shape both economic productivity—proxied by labour productivity (LP)—and environmental productivity (EP) across 221 European NUTS-2 regions from 2000 to 2019. Using panel data with fixed-effects and lagged structures, we distinguished among three types of regional capabilities: general technological, green-specific technological, and environmental scientific. This analysis contributes to understanding how regional capabilities affect productivity directly and through their interaction with GTs over time. It also advances recent efforts to differentiate general from green technological capabilities (e.g., [Mealy and Teytelboym, 2022](#)), and highlights the overlooked role of environmental scientific capabilities.

Our findings show that GTs significantly enhance EP, with effects that accumulate over time, supporting limited but growing evidence on both short- and long-term benefits (e.g. [Du and Li, 2019](#); [Ghisetti and Quatraro, 2017](#)). These results also provide empirical support to the dynamic version of the Porter Hypothesis: delayed but cumulative gains from GTs are consistent with the idea that productivity gains from green innovations emerge after knowledge accumulation and institutional adaptation through learning and scale effects ([Ambec et al., 2013](#); [Lanoie et al., 2008](#); [Piekkola and Rahko, 2024](#); [Soltmann et al., 2015](#)). In contrast, GTs yield short-lived gains in LP. These patterns suggest that while GTs support long-term value-added creation through reduced GHG emissions, their long-term influence on value-added per employee remains uncertain—highlighting the ongoing challenge of reconciling environmental and economic goals through innovation alone.

A key empirical contribution of the paper lies in demonstrating that sophisticated regional capabilities are critical enablers of both EP and LP. General sophisticated technological capabilities—proxied by economic complexity—show consistent and strong effects associated—immediate on LP and delayed on EP—with cumulative gains particularly strong for LP. Green-specific technological capabilities have more modest and lagged effects, with limited evidence of long-term influence. Environment-related scientific capabilities—measured via publication activity—exhibit significant direct and highly delayed ($t - 15$) positive effects on EP and weaker, medium-term positive effects on LP. These findings suggest that regions with strong environmental science bases are better positioned to transform scientific knowledge into either lower emissions per unit of value added or higher value-added per unit of emissions—although these effects take time. This last finding is consistent with previous evidence showing that science’s impact on productivity takes approximately two decades to materialize ([Adams, 1990](#); [Baldos et al., 2019](#)). Additionally, all three capability types positively mediate the effect of GTs on EP. Collectively, these findings underscore the importance of technological and scientific capabilities in supporting both short- and long-term productivity improvements.

Drawing on the empirical evidence, this study highlights key implications for supporting sustainable green transitions in European regions. The findings suggest that to achieve long-term gains in both economic and environmental productivity, policy efforts should not only promote GTs, but also invest in regional capabilities—skills, scientific expertise, institutional and R&D infrastructure—that enable GTs to generate tangible productivity outcomes. Given the path-dependent and place-based nature of such capabilities (Hausmann et al., 2014; Heimeriks et al., 2019; Mealy and Teytelboym, 2022), investing in green-oriented, high-value diversification pathways is critical. Importantly, the heterogeneous regional effects observed reinforce the literature’s emphasis on the uneven regional capacity to pursue dual productivity goals (Balland and Rigby, 2017). This underscores the need for designing tailored, place-based green innovation and industrial policies that align with each region’s capability endowment and recombination potential, rather than one-size-fits-all approaches. Current EU initiatives, such as the Green Deal Industrial Plan and the Net-Zero Industry Act, should support not only regions at the technological frontier, but also those with latent green diversification potential.

In line with this, the JRC (2022) and JRC (2023) reports emphasize integrating new actors and capabilities into regional strategies through Smart Specialization strategies (S3) and mission-oriented approaches.³² While current S3 initiatives has largely focused on technological related diversification (Balland et al., 2019; Montresor and Quatraro, 2020; Pintar and Essletzbichler, 2022), our findings points to the need to also strengthen regional scientific knowledge bases—particularly in environmental domains—to support long-term EP. Given the delayed yet significant effects of environmental scientific capabilities, avoiding short-termism in innovation policy is essential to realize long-term benefits. Finally, since the effects of GTs on LP are positive but not persistent over time, complementary investments in skills and workforce development are crucial. Upskilling and lifelong learning programmes should be strategically aligned with emerging regional green specializations. Integrating innovation and industrial policy with education and labour market strategies will be essential to ensure green transitions promote inclusive productivity growth and help mitigate potential labour market disruptions.

These insights align with recent contributions advocating for complex and related diversification pathways as effective routes toward sustainable transformation (Balland et al., 2019; Pintar and Essletzbichler, 2022). Nonetheless, open questions remain about how regions can build technological competitive advantages in complex activities, how policy can support capability upgrading for more complex knowledge production, and whether such strategies are universally feasible or desirable (e.g., Mewes and Broekel, 2022).

³² Smart specialization strategies refer to place-based innovation policies that aim to enhance regional competitiveness by promoting diversification into related and complex technological fields based on existing local capabilities (Balland et al., 2019; Foray et al., 2009; Pintar and Scherngell, 2022).

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7. Appendices

Appendix 1 – European NUTS-2 regions with at least one institution matched by shortest polygon distance

Shortest polygon distance applied No Yes

Appendix 2.a – Economic Complexity using the Complexity-Fitness Method

Economic complexity is implemented in three main steps.³³ First, selecting all technologies globally, defined as the 4-digit class level of the CPC classification, we constructed an annual region-by-technology specialization matrix $M_{r,i}$, using the Revealed Technological Advantage (RTA) index, representing the technology specialization portfolio of regions globally based on EPO patent data. Technologies with fewer than 40 total iterations and regions with fewer than 550 are excluded to avoid small-sample bias.³⁴ An average patent count over a three-year backward window ($t - 2$ to t) is computed for each region-technology pair, to avoid cases where a pair has not patents. The RTA index assesses technological specialization as follows:

$$RTA_{(r,i,t)} = \frac{Po_{(r,i,t)} / \mathcal{P}_i Po_{(r,i,t)}}{\mathcal{P}_c Po_{(r,i,t)} / \mathcal{P}_{r,i} Po_{(r,i,t)}} \quad (2)$$

Where $Po_{(r,i,t)}$ is the number of patents filed by inventors from region r in technology field i at the EPO in year t
 $\mathcal{P}_i Po_{(r,i,t)}$ represents the total number of patents filed by inventors from region r across all technological fields at the EPO in year t
 $\mathcal{P}_c Po_{(r,i,t)}$ denotes the total number of patents filed by inventors from all regions in technological field i at the EPO in year t
 $\mathcal{P}_{c,i} Po_{(r,i,t)}$ is the total number of patents filed by inventors from all regions across all technological fields at the EPO in year t

RTA of zero indicates no patents in a technology field, a value of one signifies the region's share matches its overall technological share (no specialization), and a value greater than one denotes positive specialization in a technological field. From the RTA, the bipartite dichotomized network $M_{r,i}$ is formed, linking region r to technology i if its RTA for the region-technology pair exceeds 1:

$$M_{r,i,t} = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } RTA_{r,i,t} \leq 1 \\ 1 & \text{if } RTA_{r,i,t} > 1 \end{cases}$$

Second, the initial fitness of a region (F_r) and the sophistication of a technology (Q_i) are both set to one for all regions and technologies:

$$Q_k^0 = 1 \quad \forall k$$

³³ The computation was performed using the economiccomplexity package in R: cran.r-project.org/web/packages/economiccomplexity/economiccomplexity.pdf

³⁴ These represent the least observed 15% of the total distribution.

$$F_i^0 = 1 \quad \forall i$$

Third, regional fitness and technology sophistication are iteratively computed and updated using the following equations (For more information, refer to the original paper of [Tacchella et al., 2012](#)):

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{F}_i^n &= \mathcal{P}_k M_{i,k} Q_k^{(n-1)} & F_i^n &= \frac{\tilde{F}_i^n}{\mathbb{I}\tilde{F}_i^{n\sim}} \\ \tilde{Q}_k^n &= \left(\frac{1}{\mathcal{P}_i M_{i,k} \frac{1}{F_i^{n-1}}} \right) & Q_k^n &= \frac{\tilde{Q}_k^n}{\mathbb{I}\tilde{Q}_k^{n\sim}} \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

Here, n represents the number of iterations, $\mathbb{I}\tilde{F}_i^{n\sim}$ is the average fitness across regions, and $\mathbb{I}\tilde{Q}_k^{n\sim}$ is the average sophistication of technologies. The first set of equations calculates (1) \tilde{F}_i^n , the estimated regional fitness, as the sum of technologies a country is specialized in, weighted by their normalized complexity from the previous iteration $Q_k^{(n-1)}$, and (2) \tilde{Q}_k^n , the technology sophistication. Technology sophistication \tilde{Q}_k^n is inversely related to the number of regions able to specialize in it ($\mathcal{P}_i M_{i,k}$), with each region weighted by the inverse of its normalized fitness from the previous iteration ($\frac{1}{F_i^{n-1}}$). Hence, technology are considered more sophisticated only if very few regions are specialized in them and if these regions have relatively high fitness scores. This captures the idea that exclusive technologies, which require advanced capabilities and are only produced by a few competitive regions, are more complex. The second set of equations normalizes these scores. F_i^n equation normalizes a region's fitness by comparing it to the global average $\mathbb{I}\tilde{F}_i^{n\sim}$, indicating whether the region is above or below average. Similarly, Q_k^n equation normalizes the sophistication of technology relative to all technologies $\mathbb{I}\tilde{Q}_k^{n\sim}$.

Appendix 2.b – Economic Complexity using the Method of Reflections

Economic complexity, based on the original Method of Reflections (MoR), is implemented as a robustness check using a similar annual region-by-technology specialization matrix $M_{r,i}$, constructed with the RTA index. The MoR, introduced by [Hidalgo and Hausmann \(2009\)](#), is an iterative linear approach that, in our context, accounts for both the diversity of a region's patent portfolio and the ubiquity of the technologies it contains. The underlying rationale is that the complexity of regions and the technologies they specialize in can be determined recursively: the complexity of a region, interpreted as its generalized diversification, is influenced by the av-

erage complexity of the technologies it specializes in, while the complexity of each technology, proxied by its ubiquity, is, in turn, driven by the complexity of the regions that hold a comparative advantage in it.

The initial diversity of knowledge production in region i , denoted d_i^0 , corresponds to the number of technological fields k in which region i is specialized. Similarly, the ubiquity of technology field k , denoted u_k^0 , reflects the number of regions specialized in k .

The MoR algorithm refines these measures through the following iterative linear process:

$$\begin{aligned} d_i^n &= \frac{1}{d_i^{(n-1)}} \mathcal{P}_k M_{ik} \cdot u_k^{(n-1)} \\ u_k^n &= \frac{1}{u_k^{(n-1)}} \mathcal{P}_i M_{ik} \cdot d_i^{(n-1)} \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

Where n denotes the number of iterations. This self-referential algorithm iteratively refines diversity and ubiquity to approximate regional and technological complexity (d_i^n, u_k^n) where each iteration builds on the information from the previous one.

The resulting d_i^n serves as a proxy for economic complexity, capturing the sophistication of a region's technological portfolio based on the types of technologies it specializes and their ubiquity.

Appendix 3 - Spearman correlation matrix (pairwise statistics)

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
1 - Environmental productivity									
2 - Labour productivity	0.56								
3 - Green patent count	0.25	0.33							
4 - Economic complexity rank	0.23	0.44	0.61						
5 - Green complexity rank	0.22	0.29	0.25	0.51					
6 - Environment-related publications	0.47	0.32	0.46	0.31	0.28				
7 - Education rate	0.40	0.38	0.27	0.24	0.29	0.44			
8 - Population density	0.62	0.49	0.12	0.16	0.14	0.24	0.23		
9 - R&D expenditure	0.42	0.54	0.62	0.57	0.28	0.37	0.49	0.28	

Appendix 4.a – Fixed effects estimates: lagged impact of green technology

	log(Environmental Productivity)	log(Labour Productivity)
$asinh(GP_{r,t-1})$	0.009 $p = 0.303$	0.005 $p = 0.244$
$asinh(GP_{r,t-3})$	0.007 $p = 0.447$	0.012 $p = 0.164$
$asinh(GP_{r,t-5})$	0.028*** $p = 0.004$	0.009 $p = 0.374$
$asinh(GP_{r,t-7})$	-0.002 $p = 0.824$	-0.0004 $p = 0.959$
$asinh(GP_{r,t-9})$	0.038*** $p = 0.010$	0.014* $p = 0.086$
Education $_{r,t-1}$	-0.143 $p = 0.285$	-0.059 $p = 0.262$
$log(PopDensity_{r,t-1})$	0.347** $p = 0.013$	-0.266*** $p = 0.000$
$log(R\&DIntensity_{r,t-1})$	0.026*** $p = 0.003$	0.019** $p = 0.039$
Adjusted R ²	0.981	0.950
Region FE	✓	✓
Year FE	✓	✓
Observations	2,274	2,274
%Obs. retained	71.2%	71.2%
F-test p-value (GP lags)	0.058	0.103

Note: Robust Driscoll-Kraay SEs. * $p < 0.1$; ** $p < 0.05$; *** $p < 0.01$

Appendix 4.b – Fixed effects estimates: lagged impact of regional general technological capabilities using the Complexity-Fitness Method (CFM) and the Method of Reflections (MoR)

	log(Environmental Productivity)		log(Labour Productivity)	
	CFM	MoR	CFM	MoR
$rank(ECI_{r,t-1})$	0.011 $p = 0.170$	0.004 $p = 0.342$	0.008 $p = 0.525$	0.006 $p = 0.339$
$rank(ECI_{r,t-3})$	0.022*** $p = 0.000$	0.005 $p = 0.399$	0.021* $p = 0.058$	-0.001 $p = 0.867$
$rank(ECI_{r,t-5})$	0.018* $p = 0.055$	0.004 $p = 0.464$	0.021*** $p = 0.003$	0.008 $p = 0.127$
$rank(ECI_{r,t-7})$	0.005 $p = 0.555$	-0.004 $p = 0.370$	0.021** $p = 0.026$	0.016*** $p = 0.000$
$rank(ECI_{r,t-9})$	-0.011* $p = 0.077$	-0.002 $p = 0.443$	0.009 $p = 0.401$	0.005 $p = 0.308$
$rank(ECI_{r,t-11})$	0.013 $p = 0.204$	0.004 $p = 0.347$	0.019** $p = 0.026$	0.004 $p = 0.240$
$rank(ECI_{r,t-13})$	0.015*** $p = 0.003$	0.008** $p = 0.050$	0.016* $p = 0.078$	0.008*** $p = 0.003$
$rank(ECI_{r,t-15})$	0.013* $p = 0.051$	0.005 $p = 0.248$	0.006 $p = 0.439$	0.003 $p = 0.203$
$asinh(GP_{r,t-1})$	0.010 $p = 0.133$	0.012 $p = 0.140$	0.018** $p = 0.020$	0.018* $p = 0.055$
Education $_{r,t-1}$	0.220** $p = 0.032$	0.261** $p = 0.020$	0.063 $p = 0.351$	0.117 $p = 0.134$
$log(PopDensity_{r,t-1})$	0.101** $p = 0.021$	0.104** $p = 0.015$	-0.530** $p = 0.024$	-0.527** $p = 0.024$
$log(R\&DIntensity_{r,t-1})$	0.022*** $p = 0.000$	0.028*** $p = 0.001$	0.010 $p = 0.448$	0.017 $p = 0.192$
Adjusted R ²	0.981	0.981	0.950	0.950
Region FE	✓	✓	✓	✓
Year FE	✓	✓	✓	✓
Observations	2,386	2,386	2,386	2,386
%Obs. retained	74.7%	74.7%	74.7%	74.7%
F-test p-value (Complexity lags)	0.077	0.718	0.002	0.168

Note: Robust Driscoll-Kraay SEs. *p<0.1; **p<0.05; ***p<0.01

Appendix 4.c – Fixed effects estimates: lagged impact of regional green technological capabilities using the original Green Complexity Index (GCI) and the alternative GCI using Green ECI

	log(Environmental Productivity)		log(Labour Productivity)	
	GCI	Alternative GCI	GCI	Alternative GCI
$rank(GCI_{r,t-1})$	0.003** $p = 0.033$	0.003* $p = 0.053$	0.001 $p = 0.564$	0.001 $p = 0.605$
$rank(GCI_{r,t-3})$	0.004** $p = 0.041$	0.004** $p = 0.034$	0.001 $p = 0.655$	0.001 $p = 0.676$
$rank(GCI_{r,t-5})$	0.004* $p = 0.085$	0.004* $p = 0.094$	0.005** $p = 0.034$	0.005** $p = 0.036$
$rank(GCI_{r,t-7})$	-0.001 $p = 0.678$	-0.001 $p = 0.625$	0.001 $p = 0.681$	0.001 $p = 0.680$
$rank(GCI_{r,t-9})$	0.002 $p = 0.344$	0.002 $p = 0.319$	0.0001 $p = 0.953$	0.0003 $p = 0.909$
$rank(GCI_{r,t-11})$	-0.0004 $p = 0.926$	-0.0002 $p = 0.957$	0.001 $p = 0.679$	0.001 $p = 0.702$
$rank(GCI_{r,t-13})$	0.003 $p = 0.511$	0.003 $p = 0.489$	0.002 $p = 0.376$	0.002 $p = 0.365$
$rank(GCI_{r,t-15})$	0.002 $p = 0.356$	0.003 $p = 0.302$	-0.002 $p = 0.570$	-0.002 $p = 0.531$
$asinh(GP_{r,t-1})$	0.020* $p = 0.053$	0.020* $p = 0.053$	0.013* $p = 0.061$	0.013* $p = 0.062$
Education $_{r,t-1}$	-0.095 $p = 0.394$	-0.093 $p = 0.402$	-0.275*** $p = 0.000$	-0.275*** $p = 0.000$
$log(PopDensity_{r,t-1})$	0.708*** $p = 0.000$	0.710*** $p = 0.000$	-0.197** $p = 0.014$	-0.197** $p = 0.014$
$log(R\&DIntensity_{r,t-1})$	0.034*** $p = 0.000$	0.034*** $p = 0.000$	0.003 $p = 0.856$	0.003 $p = 0.862$
Adjusted R ²	0.981	0.981	0.950	0.950
Region FE	✓	✓	✓	✓
Year FE	✓	✓	✓	✓
Observations	1,670	1,670	1,670	1,670
%Obs. retained	52.3%	52.3%	52.3%	52.3%
F-test p-value (Green Complexity lags)	0.418	0.380	0.206	0.193

Note: Robust Driscoll-Kraay SEs. * $p < 0.1$; ** $p < 0.05$; *** $p < 0.01$

Appendix 4.d – Fixed effects estimates: lagged impact of regional environmental scientific capabilities using the original EnvScience identification based on MAG classification (MAG) and the alternative EnvScience using a keyword list

	<i>log</i> (Environmental Productivity)		<i>log</i> (Labour Productivity)	
	MAG	Alternative EnvScience	MAG	Alternative EnvScience
<i>asinh</i> (EnvScience _{<i>r,t-1</i>})	0.052*** <i>p</i> = 0.005	0.031* <i>p</i> = 0.053	0.021* <i>p</i> = 0.080	0.007 <i>p</i> = 0.648
<i>asinh</i> (EnvScience _{<i>r,t-3</i>})	-0.005 <i>p</i> = 0.816	-0.008 <i>p</i> = 0.703	0.011 <i>p</i> = 0.351	0.005 <i>p</i> = 0.598
<i>asinh</i> (EnvScience _{<i>r,t-5</i>})	0.006 <i>p</i> = 0.814	-0.008 <i>p</i> = 0.676	0.022** <i>p</i> = 0.024	0.011 <i>p</i> = 0.178
<i>asinh</i> (EnvScience _{<i>r,t-7</i>})	-0.049* <i>p</i> = 0.076	-0.011 <i>p</i> = 0.593	-0.016 <i>p</i> = 0.293	0.021** <i>p</i> = 0.036
<i>asinh</i> (EnvScience _{<i>r,t-9</i>})	-0.031* <i>p</i> = 0.080	0.033*** <i>p</i> = 0.008	-0.009 <i>p</i> = 0.501	0.011 <i>p</i> = 0.424
<i>asinh</i> (EnvScience _{<i>r,t-11</i>})	0.008 <i>p</i> = 0.756	-0.004 <i>p</i> = 0.842	-0.003 <i>p</i> = 0.860	0.0002 <i>p</i> = 0.988
<i>asinh</i> (EnvScience _{<i>r,t-13</i>})	0.014 <i>p</i> = 0.362	-0.010 <i>p</i> = 0.584	-0.026*** <i>p</i> = 0.007	-0.028*** <i>p</i> = 0.002
<i>asinh</i> (EnvScience _{<i>r,t-15</i>})	0.052*** <i>p</i> = 0.003	0.056** <i>p</i> = 0.019	0.008 <i>p</i> = 0.696	-0.008 <i>p</i> = 0.527
<i>asinh</i> (GP _{<i>r,t-1</i>})	0.006 <i>p</i> = 0.578	0.006 <i>p</i> = 0.564	0.006 <i>p</i> = 0.201	0.005 <i>p</i> = 0.199
Education _{<i>r,t-1</i>}	-0.002 <i>p</i> = 0.989	-0.003 <i>p</i> = 0.980	0.073* <i>p</i> = 0.085	0.074* <i>p</i> = 0.058
<i>log</i> (PopDensity _{<i>r,t-1</i>})	0.481*** <i>p</i> = 0.000	0.427*** <i>p</i> = 0.001	-0.292*** <i>p</i> = 0.000	-0.275*** <i>p</i> = 0.001
<i>log</i> (R&DIntensity _{<i>r,t-1</i>})	0.031** <i>p</i> = 0.018	0.046*** <i>p</i> = 0.001	0.033*** <i>p</i> = 0.002	0.036*** <i>p</i> = 0.002
Adjusted R ²	0.982	0.982	0.951	0.951
Region FE	✓	✓	✓	✓
Year FE	✓	✓	✓	✓
Observations	1,968	1,968	1,968	1,968
%Obs. retained	63.9%	63.4%	63.9%	63.4%
F-test p-value (EnvScience lags)	0.059	0.039	0.099	0.236

Note: Robust Driscoll-Kraay SEs. **p*<0.1; ***p*<0.05; ****p*<0.01

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